

ExtremeXP

Experiment Driven and User Experience Oriented Analytics for
Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions

D4.1: Visualisation and explainability service

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable (D4.1) presents the design and implementation of the User Interaction Module of the ExtremeXP framework, developed under Tasks 4.1 and 4.2. The module provides a unified environment that allows users to monitor, analyse, and guide experiments through integrated visualization and explainability services. The Visualization User Interface supports experiment monitoring, comparative analysis, and human-in-the-loop interaction, while the Explainability Module incorporates model- and pipeline-level methods to interpret model behaviour and experimental configurations. The deliverable also introduces scalable techniques for interactive visual exploration of large datasets, combining adaptive indexing and approximate query processing to ensure responsive visualization. Finally, the Flood Visualizer (VR) and Virtual Dashboard (AR) prototypes extend explainable experimentation into mixed-reality environments. Together, these developments advance transparent, human-centered, and trustworthy experimentation within ExtremeXP.</p>
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Table of contents

Version History	4
Table of contents	5
List of Figures.....	7
List of Tables.....	9
List of Acronyms	10
Executive Summary	12
Introduction.....	13
1 Requirements.....	14
1.1 Research objectives	14
1.2 Literature review	14
1.3 Requirements from use cases.....	16
Summary.....	18
2 User Interaction Module	18
2.1 Position within the ExtremeXP Framework.....	18
2.2 User Interaction Module Architecture	19
2.2.1 Visualization User Interface (UI)	20
2.2.2 Visualization Middleware	20
2.2.3 Explainability Module	21
2.3 From experiment specifications to visualizations	22
3 Visualization User Interface	22
3.1 Experiment Monitoring Page.....	23
3.2 Workflow Analysis Page	24
3.3 Comparative Analysis Page.....	30
3.4 Human in the loop tasks in ExtremeXP	34
4 Techniques for Scalable Interactive Visual Exploration.....	36
4.1 Adaptive Indexing for Approximate Query Answering in 2D Visual Exploration.....	37
4.2 Visualization-aware Time-Series Caching	41
4.3 Time-Series Caching for Scalable Interactive Visualization and Pattern Search	44
5 Explainability Module.....	47
5.1 ML Model Explainability.....	48
5.1.1 Supported Methods.....	48
5.1.2 Global Counterfactual Explanations for an ML Model.....	50
5.1.3 Spatial Feature Attribution	52

5.2 ML Pipeline Explainability	54
5.2.1 Hyperparameter Effect Explainability	54
5.2.2 Counterfactual Pipeline Explainability	56
5.3 Implementation and Integration of the Explainability Module.....	58
5.3.1 Integration with the Visualization UI	59
6 Immersive Visualization Tools for Explainability and User Engagement.....	61
6.1 Overview	61
6.2 3D Flood Visualizer for UC1 (Flash-Flood Use Case)	61
6.2.1 Objective	61
6.2.2 Implementation	61
6.2.3 Scientific and Practical Relevance of the VR Approach	63
6.3 Virtual Dashboard for Explainable Analytics.....	64
6.3.1 Objectives	64
6.3.2 Implementation	64
6.3.3 Scientific and Practical Relevance.....	65
6.4 Summary.....	65
Conclusions.....	67
Appendix A - Explanation User Interface (XUI) Design Patterns.....	70
References.....	76

List of Figures

Figure 1: Interactions of the User Interaction module.	19
Figure 2: Experiment Monitoring Page showing workflow progress, execution table, and parameter–metric visualization.	23
Figure 3: Workflow Analysis Page providing a detailed view of workflow parameters, metrics, and artifacts organized by task, and serving as an entry point for detailed model performance analysis and explainability.	25
Figure 4: Data Exploration View showing available chart options; a line chart is displayed in this example.	26
Figure 5: Data Exploration View showing two map-based visualizations: trajectories (bottom) and heatmap-based density overlays (top).	27
Figure 6: Model Insights Section showing model performance visualizations.	28
Figure 7: Instance View showing test data, predictions, and ground-truth values.	29
Figure 8: Counterfactual Explanations View within the Instance View, showing misclassified instances on a scatter plot and their corresponding counterfactuals below.	29
Figure 9: Feature Explainability View showing feature-level effects using feature importance, PDP, ALE plots.	30
Figure 10: Hyperparameter Explainability View providing insights into relationships between training configurations and model performance.	30
Figure 11: Workflow Comparison Page showing the Metrics Tab for quantitative comparison of performance across workflows.	31
Figure 12: Workflow Comparison Page - Model Insights Tab displaying confusion matrices for selected workflows.	32
Figure 13: Instance View within the Model Insights Tab showing per-instance prediction comparisons across workflows.	33
Figure 14: The Data Tab presents side-by-side visualizations of dataset features across workflows, offering an overview of data characteristics for comparative analysis.	34
Figure 15 Example of a custom interactive Human-in-the-Loop task interface embedded in the Visualization UI, enabling expert validation during workflow execution.	36
Figure 16: Example of the VALINOR-A index structure. (a) Raw data objects with their attributes and file offsets; (b) hierarchical tiling of the data space; (c) detailed view of a tile containing approximate metadata, sampled objects, and a bitmap indicating sampled entries.	39
Figure 17: Impact of user-defined error bound on total query time.	41
Figure 18: Query Evaluation over MinMaxCache.	42
Figure 19: TimeVizBench User Interface for the interactive benchmarking of methods for large-scale time series exploration.	44
Figure 20: System Overview for SkeTSCache. A user issues a visualization or a pattern query. Each query is processed separately but utilizes the same cached data; managed by the Cache Manager.	45

Figure 21: Execution time distribution comparison of SkeTSCache variants and baseline methods across INTL, MNF, and SOCC datasets. M4 [∞] -C achieves the lowest median execution time with minimal outliers, while separate-backend approaches (MinMaxCache, M4-NoC) suffer from heavy-tail latency spikes.....	46
Figure 22: Model Explainability as seen through the Visualization UI.....	49
Figure 23: User Interface for the Global Counterfactual Explanations.....	51
Figure 24: Global Counterfactual Explanation. Action Selection Scatter Plots.....	52
Figure 25: Example output of the Spatial Attribution component for Use Case 1.	53
Figure 26: PD plot for Pipeline Explainability. The x-axis shows feature “epochs”, the y-axis the average predicted accuracy. We observe that increasing the value of “epochs” improves the model’s accuracy.	55
Figure 27: 2D PD plot for Pipeline Explainability. The x-axis shows the “epochs” hyperparameter, the y-axis shows “batch_size”, and the colour scale indicates accuracy values. We observe that low values for “epochs” and “batch size” result in the lowest combined accuracy.....	56
Figure 28: ALE Plot for Pipeline Explainability. The x-axis shows feature “epochs”, y-axis shows the average predicted effect on accuracy. We observe that higher values of “epochs” contribute a positive effect on model’s accuracy.	56
Figure 29: Overview of the 3D Flood Visualizer showing the predicted flood extent and depth within an urban area. The visualization, rendered in Unity using Cesium 3D Maps, allows immersive spatial inspection of flood predictions and comparison against ground-truth data.	62
Figure 30: Immersive viewpoint inside the Flood Visualizer. Users can navigate freely, enabling explainability and assessment of the flood situation.	63
Figure 31: Interactive visualization of analytical results within the Virtual Dashboard. The AR interface enables users to inspect performance metrics and model behaviour using hand gestures in an immersive workspace.	64
Figure 32: Comparison view in the Virtual Dashboard showing multiple experiment results plotted together. The module supports visualization of accuracy and latency metrics, allowing users to compare alternative configurations interactively.	65

List of Tables

Table 1: Pattern search accuracy metrics using First/Last slope computation across three real-world datasets, for the SkeTSCache approximate variants.	47
Table 2: Preliminary results of our counterfactual explainability framework on the Cybersecurity Use Case task.	58
Table 3: Progress on relevant KPIs.....	67

List of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALE	Accumulated Local Effects
API	Application Programming Interface
AQP	Approximate Query Processing
AR	Augmented Reality
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DAL	Data Abstraction Layer
DDM	Decentralised Data Management
DiCE	Diverse Counterfactual Explanations
DNS	Domain Name System
DSL	Domain-Specific Language
FL	First/Last
GCE	Global Counterfactual Explanation
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IG	Integrated Gradients
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MLP	Multi-layer Perceptron
MUI	Material UI
NFA	Non-deterministic Finite Automata
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
PDP	Partial Dependence Plots
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UMAP	Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection
VAE	Variational Autoencoder

VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work package
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
XUI	Explanation User Interface

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D4.1) reports on the design, development, and research outcomes of **Tasks 4.1 and 4.2**, which together form the **User Interaction Module** of the ExtremeXP framework. The module provides a unified environment that enables users to monitor, analyse, and steer experiments through integrated visualization and explainability services. It constitutes the main human-facing entry point of the ExtremeXP system, bridging automated experimentation with interactive analysis and decision-making.

The module integrates three core components:

- **Visualization User Interface**, supporting experiment monitoring, comparative analysis, dataset exploration, and human-in-the-loop interaction;
- **Visualization Middleware**, connecting the interface with the ExtremeXP data services to ensure scalable and interactive access to experimental data and results;
- **Explainability Module**, offering a broad set of model- and pipeline-level explainability methods, including feature attribution, partial dependence, accumulated local effects, and counterfactual analysis.

Complementary research under Task 4.1 introduced **scalable techniques for interactive visual exploration**, combining adaptive indexing and approximate query processing to deliver low-latency analytics over large datasets. These include methods for 2D visual exploration, time-series analysis, and pattern search; all designed to maintain real-time responsiveness even on raw or high-volume data.

The deliverable also presents **immersive analytics prototypes**—the *Flood Visualizer* (VR) and *Virtual Dashboard* (AR)—which extend explainable experimentation into three-dimensional and mixed-reality environments, enhancing user understanding, engagement, and trust.

Together, these developments realize ExtremeXP's vision of **transparent, human-guided experimentation**. The User Interaction Module transforms the outputs of automated experimentation into interpretable insights, strengthens the integration between visualization and explainability, and establishes a foundation for **trustworthy, experimentation-driven analytics** within the project.

Introduction

In D4.1, we report on the design, technical, and research work performed in the context of Tasks 4.1 and 4.2. Since there is a significant synergy between these two tasks, we present them jointly.

Task 4.1 aims to develop techniques for efficient, explorative, and adaptive visualization of various types of extreme data. This involves creating data structures, such as efficient in-memory indexes, to support low-latency interactions that visually process millions of data points or involve complex analytical tasks. Additionally, it aims to provide a model of visual interactions on experiment-based analytics and visual UIs to support the analysis of experiment-based analytics. Task 4.2 focuses on enhancing trustworthiness by providing visual-based explanations. The joint work from these tasks will be integrated into a comprehensive visualization framework that caters to the needs of the experimental workflow, supporting the user in making informed decisions, performing human-in-the-loop tasks, and providing user feedback.

Together, these two tasks form the **User Interaction Module** of the ExtremeXP framework—a central component that enables users to remain in the loop throughout the experimentation lifecycle. After defining an experiment in the ExtremeXP DSL and initiating its execution, users can monitor its progress, analyse the produced metrics, explore input, and output datasets, interpret explainability results, and ultimately steer further experimentation based on the derived insights. The module's main objective is to transform the large volumes of data and model outputs produced by automated experimentation into **transparent, explainable, and human-interpretable insights**. By combining interactive visualization, scalable analytics, and explainability techniques within a unified environment, it strengthens ExtremeXP's core mission of enabling **experimentation-driven analytics through human-guided understanding and validation**.

This deliverable is closely **complementary to D4.2**, as both address the **human-in-the-loop dimension** of the ExtremeXP framework. While D4.2 focuses on **intent capture and workflow generation**—anticipating user goals and supporting the design of complex analytical workflows through adaptive, gamified mechanisms (*design time*)—D4.1 emphasizes the **user-facing components** that operate once experiments have been launched (*runtime*). It covers the **visual and analytical interfaces** through which users monitor progress, analyse and interpret results, and explore explainable insights, thereby closing the loop between observation, interpretation, and re-execution. Together, these deliverables realize the ExtremeXP vision of a **continuous, human-in-the-loop experimentation cycle**—from intent specification and workflow generation to interactive visualization, analysis, and explainable reasoning.

The remainder of this document is organized as follows. **Section 1** outlines the requirements that guided the development of the implemented methods and techniques, introducing the underlying research goals and reviewing relevant state-of-the-art approaches in visualization and explainability, particularly in the context of experiment analytics. **Section 2** presents the **User Interaction Module**, describing its role within the ExtremeXP architecture and its main components. **Section 3** focuses on the **Visualization User Interface**, summarizing its key pages and functionalities for experiment monitoring, workflow analysis, comparative visualization, and human-in-the-loop interaction. **Section 4** discusses the **techniques for scalable interactive visual exploration**, while **Section 5** details the **Explainability Module**, including both model- and pipeline-level methods, counterfactual and spatial explanations, and its integration with the visualization environment. Finally, **Section 6** introduces the **immersive analytics components**, namely the Flood Visualizer and Virtual Dashboard, which extend explainable experimentation into virtual and augmented-reality environments.

1 Requirements

This section presents the requirements that guided the development of methods and techniques implemented in the Visualization module and the Explainability module. We first introduce the research goals. Then, we briefly review state-of-the-art solutions for visualization and explainability, especially in the context of experiment analytics. Finally, we present the requirements coming from the project use cases, described in D6.1, that guided our work.

1.1 Research objectives

According to the ExtremeXP description of work the tasks 4.1 and 4.2 have the following goals:

- Explore how visual analytics, augmented reality and other visualisation techniques and their combinations can enhance user experience for different use cases, actors, domains, applications, and problem areas.
- Summarise the findings into design guidelines, user interface pattern libraries, and component libraries.
- Support interactive visual analytics with low latency that are adapted to diverse user exploration patterns for extreme data characteristics (e.g., volumes not fitting in main memory, fast streaming data).
- Develop explanation methods about the decision-making process of the system and significantly improve the usability, expressiveness, and experience of end users.

More specifically, the work reported here focuses on the visualization aspects of the ExtremeXP framework. It aims to provide an interface between the framework and its users, where the system supports the analysis and explanation of experiment results through rich, interactive, and intuitive visualizations, enabling users to explore, interpret, and steer the experimentation process.

In doing so, it advances R&D on explorative visualization, visual analytics, augmented reality (AR), and explainability.

1.2 Literature review

MLOps Tracking & Monitoring. Modern machine learning development relies on MLOps platforms that support experiment tracking, pipeline orchestration, model versioning, and deployment. Tools like MLflow [1], Neptune [2] and Weights & Biases (W&B) [3] are central to this ecosystem, yet their approach to user interaction and visualization reveals a **significant gap between passive monitoring and truly interactive, human-in-the-loop analytics.**

Current MLOps tools primarily treat visualization as a means of inspecting basic metrics logged during experiment execution. They store metadata, metrics, and artifacts (e.g., trained models) to support reproducibility and comparison, but their visualization features are largely confined to scalar metrics and artifact listings, with minimal support for interactively exploring input or output data. To gain deeper visual insights, users must manually generate plots during a run and log them as static artifacts.

MLflow, for instance, provides a basic interface for tracking parameters, metrics, and artifacts, with only limited built-in visualization options. Additional plots can be created programmatically (e.g., using matplotlib), but they must be logged as static files to appear in the interface. Even more capable analytics platforms such as Neptune primarily focus on pre-defined, logged metrics and still lack facilities for interactive analysis of the underlying data artifacts.

Furthermore, the integration of explainability within MLOps platforms remains limited. Most explainability tools operate independently of experiment tracking systems, making it difficult to link insights about model behaviour back to the specific experiments, code versions, and data that produced them. In a typical MLOps workflow, an explanation is treated as just another static artifact—such as an image of a feature-importance plot—generated by a script and logged during execution. This static approach prevents users from interactively generating explanations for different data subsets or comparing the internal logic of models across workflows within a unified interface.

In addition, current tools offer limited support for human-in-the-loop experimentation. Once an experiment is launched, users typically cannot interactively control its execution from within the same analytics interface, for example by pausing or resuming runs, prioritizing certain executions, terminating unpromising ones based on intermediate results, or launching new runs with modified parameters derived from ongoing analysis. This lack of interactive control hinders adaptive experimentation and limits opportunities for guided exploration during training and evaluation.

From this analysis, **we gather three key limitations in existing tools:**

- A focus on metric monitoring over **explorative data analysis**.
- A lack of deep, interactive integration of **explainability** methods.
- An absence of user interfaces designed for **dynamic, in-flight experiment control, and modification**.

The Visualization Module of the ExtremeXP framework is designed to address these gaps. It shifts the paradigm from passive monitoring to active, **human-in-the-loop** experimentation by providing a unified environment for **dynamic data exploration, integrated visual explainability, and interactive control over the entire experiment lifecycle**.

Explainability. As the adoption of machine learning (ML) systems becomes increasingly widespread in critical domains, the demand for transparent, interpretable, and trustworthy ML models is pivotal for different user groups including end-users of AI infused systems. End-users can be, for example, passengers using an app from a public transport provider, domain experts using AI in decision-making, e.g. transport planners, the data scientists and ML engineers responsible for ML model development, refinement, and oversight as well as regulators and auditors. Ehsan et al. [4] argues that explainability is crucial for accountability for AI systems and their produces. To support ethical human-AI interaction, users need to understand and contest AI decisions. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) aims to address this demand by providing users with insights into how and why models make certain predictions. While early work in XAI has mostly focused on visualizing internal model mechanisms or providing post-hoc explanations, recent research emphasises the *interactive and functional roles* that explainability plays, especially for expert users engaged in complex and time-critical ML workflows.

Explainability through Interaction Lens. Recent research has underscored that explanation in AI systems should not be treated as a one-time output, but rather as part of a *social and iterative process*—a dialogue between the human and the machine [4], [5]. Chromik and Butz [5] conceptualize the **Explanation User Interface (XUI)** as the full set of outputs and controls through which users interact with an XAI system. Their review introduces multiple modes of human-XAI interaction, the most relevant in our context being: (1) **information transmission**, where users passively receive explanations; (2) **interaction as dialogue**, where users can probe the system iteratively and get feedback; (3) **interaction as control**, where explanations from XUI provide feedback on how to change parameters of the ML model or its data to adjust its behaviour; and (4) **interaction as tool use**, where XUI acts as lens on a domain to help users gain insights in domain-specific data. These modes help

distinguish between one-way explanation mechanisms and interactive, dynamic systems that foster user engagement, learning, and ultimately, better system control.

Supporting Model Control, Debugging, and Refinement. Similarly to interaction as control mode, Kalasampath et al. [6] argue, that explainability offers *clear, actionable insights* into model behaviour, which are indispensable for tasks such as feature selection, hyperparameter tuning, and identifying model biases. While Mohammadkhani et al. [7] show that in software engineering contexts, XAI is instrumental for **debugging** model behaviour and detecting issues in the training data or model architecture. For instance, saliency-based methods can expose a model's overreliance on irrelevant features (e.g., background pixels in image classification), prompting corrective action.

Refinement through explanation is further supported by tools like **SHAP** and **LIME**, which quantify feature importance and help prioritize modeling efforts. Visualization tools such as **Partial Dependence Plots (PDP)** and **Accumulated Local Effects (ALE)** plots can reveal non-linear feature relationships and unexpected interactions, guiding further data transformations or feature engineering. Moreover, **Influence Functions** identify training data points that most significantly affect a prediction, offering insights into dataset quality and representativeness [8]. Papastefanatos G, et al. [9] demonstrated how users can visually explore and perform analytic operations directly on raw data files, significantly streamlining analysis tasks and saving time on manual data cleaning and preparation.

Such capabilities empower users not only to interpret a model's decision-making but also to iteratively improve it. Schwalbe and Finzel [8] argue that the choice of an XAI method should be grounded in a thorough use-case analysis that reflects the **actionability** of the explanation, i.e., how it enables the user to take corrective or optimizing steps. They highlight the importance of choosing between **local** and **global** explanation techniques depending on the task: local methods (e.g., LIME and SHAP) clarify why a model made a specific prediction on that dataset, while global methods (e.g., Partial Dependence Plots) reveal broader patterns and show how the model behaves on average.

Finally, there is growing interest in integrating multiple explanation methods into a unified framework that supports not just prediction explanation, but also **explanation of the entire ML pipeline**. Ehsan et al. [4] argue for consideration of the entire AI lifecycle by clarifying the *who* (diverse stakeholders), *why* (explainability goals), *when* (trust calibration), and *where* (application domain) explanations are needed.

1.3 Requirements from use cases

Use Case 1 (UC1) focuses on flash floods. Flash floods pose significant risks, especially in urban areas. Current hydrological models based on physical properties rely on vast amounts of data and take a long time to process, thus making rapid forecasting a challenge. The Flash Flood Prediction use case (UC1) focuses on AI-driven flash floods forecasting. UC1 trains the AI model based on the hydrological model as its ground truth to reduce input data requirements and speed up the forecasting process. Since the data is map-based, UC1 benefits from the ability to perform visual comparisons between AI-based forecasts and traditional hydrodynamic models. When comparing the forecasts with the hydrodynamic models, UC1 users need to see the models' accuracies and mean time to complete as well as the effects of variability points. In the data preprocessing stage, users need tools to check for missing data in time-series datasets, ensuring data integrity before running simulations. End users for UC1 need moreover to understand the uncertainty associated with the results, in terms of temporality and location. This implies that Sensitivity Analyses and Uncertainty Quantification are needed for UC1.

Hence, the following **requirements** are considered to be of particular relevance for visualization and decision support in the context of UC1:

1. The user interface of the demonstrator allows us to define the variability points as well as to control scenarios of execution. The user interface also permits the user to access results analysis. The operator should be able to visualize flood maps produced by the hydrodynamic or AI forecast model onto a basemap.
2. The visualisation reflects the difference between several models, specifically the output of the model prediction, the historical data, and the historical records. The visualisation moreover reflects the accuracy of the forecasting obtained from different AI models.

Use Case 2 (UC2) focuses on enhancing cybersecurity situation awareness to improve threat mitigation. AI-driven threat detection is being explored to address the limitations posed by traditional security mechanisms. UC2 demonstrator aims to simulate real-world attack scenarios, improving the detection and classification of cyber threats by analysing the behaviour of threat actors and correlating cyber threats. To do so, operators must be able to classify threats, provide feedback, and modify detection models by looking at correlation of attack steps, justification for detected anomalies, and similarity scoring of threats. UC2 therefore focuses on graphical threat visualizations, as well as on providing justifications for detected anomalies from AI analysis. Since users will need to explore the outputs, the platform should support interactive components such as filtering, highlighting, and zooming into different parameters. Hence, the following **requirements** are considered to be of particular relevance for visualization and decision support in the context of UC2:

- The security operator is able to make proper decisions and observations through the graphical and technique-based knowledge representation of the threat.
- The detected and correlated threat techniques are visualisable as kill chains.

The two focal **performance** aspects are: (1) false positives and negatives on threat techniques classification; and (2) mean time to classification compared to traditional human techniques.

Use Case 3 (UC3) provides situational intelligence and decision-making tools for public protection and disaster relief (PPDR) with the focus on first responders dealing with fire incidents in urban areas. The system is designed to provide fire detection through video surveillance; recommend the appropriate actions based on the context and information available through messages and other sensors, as well as to optimize first responder flow and response time. Hence, the detected fire and contactable personnels being visualised on a map is considered to be the **requirement** of particular relevance for visualization and decision support in the context of UC3.

Use Case 4 (UC4) develops a transportation analysis platform, called MobyApp, that can provide simulations and data analytics, and visualizations to improve decision-making for transportation planners, authorities, and modelers. AI and extreme data analytics are used to enhance transportation forecasts and policy assessments such as zero-emission freight zones, autonomous vehicles, and remote work effects on urban mobility. UC4 introduces the need for visualization of user mobility patterns in geo-locations and on timeline, in order to explore the data and the predictions. Hence, enabling adaptive visualizations of extreme data, both during data collections and also for simulation results, is considered to be the **requirement** of particular relevance for visualization and decision support in the context of UC4.

Use Case 5 (UC5) concentrates on failure prevention in the manufacturing industry through predictive maintenance and real-time anomaly detection, as machine uptime is essential for maintaining high system availability and competitiveness. UC5 develops a dashboard for technical service teams for automatic detection of failures in machine components such as heads, ball screws, and axes. To test AI models under various failure scenarios, UC5 will use simulated data. To make sure that correct data

is selected, UC5 needs to be able to visualize time series data from vibrations, power readings, and more. Due to machines having diverse configurations, the UC5 has a variety of variability points that will affect the AI model training. Handling high volumes of data points in a clear and understandable manner is critical for UC5. Hence, the following **requirements** are considered to be of particular relevance for visualization and decision support in the context of UC5:

1. The user can, through fingerprint visualization, inspect the historical progression of fingerprints of the results.
2. The user can easily explore time series via an adequate visualization method.
3. Algorithm effectiveness, i.e., the machine operator must be able to evaluate whether the result is correct or not.
4. The data analyst should compare the results obtained by the AI model with the feedback of the machine operator in order to measure the detection capacity of the algorithm.
5. In the demonstrator, the variability points regard the selection of the AI models for prediction and its parameters.

The main **performance** aspect is the number of data points while ensuring a smooth and manipulable visualization for the user.

Summary

In summary, requirements for the use cases emphasise the need for advanced interactive visualization tools that facilitate the exploration of variability points and their effects on model outcomes. A significant focus is placed on explainability, ensuring users can interpret AI model decisions and understand the rationale behind anomalies. User interaction is critical, requiring adaptive visualizations that allow selection of data, result types, and feedback provision. Furthermore, the system should offer explanations for AI/ML model decisions, to improve model transparency and trust, particularly in use cases like UC2. These requirements guide the selection and design of visualization tools, user interfaces, and explanation methods within the overall explainability framework. The ability to track the time taken for model processing is moreover needed, as performance is emphasized in the context of model accuracy and processing time. These requirements align with the project's expected results (ER), particularly ER6 (explainability-oriented user interaction toolset) and ER7 (interactive visualization support), and map to key performance indicators KPI 5.1 (applicability of the visualisation techniques), KPI 5.4 (response time in visual analytics) and KPI 5.5 (enhancement of trust with explanations) across the use cases.

2 User Interaction Module

2.1 Position within the ExtremeXP Framework

The ExtremeXP experimentation framework¹ provides an end-to-end environment for experimentation-driven analytics. At its core, it enables users to specify experiments, execute them, analyse the resulting data and outcomes, and use these insights to guide subsequent iterations. The process begins with experiment specification, which can be achieved through a dedicated DSL, supported by textual and graphical editors, or through an intent-based editor that captures high-level user goals. These specifications are then interpreted by the experimentation engine, which orchestrates one or more workflows on an execution engine. The results of these workflows—including datasets, models, metrics, and logs—are collected and managed by the framework's data services: the Data Abstraction Layer, which stores and queries executed experiments and workflows,

¹ More details on the overall ExtremeXP framework can be found in Deliverable 5.1.

and the Decentralised Data Management system, which manages datasets and artifacts. To ensure secure and consistent access across all components, the framework integrates a unified access control mechanism.

On top of these capabilities, a set of user-facing components transform experimental results into actionable insights. At the centre of these lies the **User Interaction Module**. It connects to the Data Abstraction Layer and the Decentralised Data Management system, enabling users to explore results through intuitive visualisations, interpret them with explanation mechanisms, and derive insights that guide the experimentation process while keeping the user in the loop.

2.2 User Interaction Module Architecture

The **User Interaction Module** represents the practical outcome of Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 and constitutes the main entry point for human users in the ExtremeXP framework to examine and analyse the experiment results. It is designed to ensure that humans remain in the loop during the execution of experiments. The module retrieves data from various ExtremeXP repositories to generate visualisations and explanations, providing users with critical insights necessary for expert decision-making.

Figure 1: Interactions of the User Interaction module.

Figure 1 illustrates the interactions of the User Interaction Module within the overall ExtremeXP architecture. The module comprises three main components: the Visualization User Interface (UI), the Visualization Middleware, and the Explainability Module.

2.2.1 Visualization User Interface (UI)

The Visualization User Interface (UI) is designed to enable users to monitor, control, and interact with experiments, visually analyse their results, and support human-in-the-loop tasks. Its main functionalities include:

- **Explorative analytics:** users can interactively explore experiment outputs, datasets, and metrics through visualizations, filters, and comparisons, uncovering patterns and insights that guide subsequent experimentation.
- **Monitoring and control:** users can track the progress of experiments and manage their lifecycle in real time, including starting, stopping, or pausing entire experiments or individual workflows.
- **Dynamic experiment design:** users can visually examine the results of completed or running workflows and adjust the design of experiments on the fly. This includes modifying execution parameters such as workflow scheduling order or dynamically adding new workflows based on insights from variability points.
- **Explainability insights:** users can explore the results of explainability methods directly within the UI, such as counterfactuals and feature importance, enabling a deeper understanding of experimental outcomes.

The UI itself is composed of four sub-components:

- **Visualization Metamodel**, which defines how experiment data, workflows, and results are represented and mapped to visual elements such as filters, tables, and charts,
- **Visual Explainability module**, which integrates explanation methods into the visual interface and couples them with experiment results for interactive exploration,
- **Visualization Toolkit**, which provides reusable visualization methods and components for rendering and interacting with experiment data at scale, and
- **UI Interactor**, which manages user actions, maintains interaction state, and connects front-end operations to the underlying services of the ExtremeXP framework.

2.2.2 Visualization Middleware

Visualization Middleware acts as an intermediary between the Visualization UI and the data repositories of the ExtremeXP platform. Its main objective is to ensure efficient interaction during the visual exploration and analysis of large datasets. It receives requests from the UI related to experiment inputs, outputs, or metrics, and coordinates their retrieval, processing, and optimization to deliver responsive, high-quality visualizations. The middleware is implemented in Java 17 using the Spring Framework and exposes REST APIs that are consumed by the Visualization UI. For efficient query processing over data files, it integrates the DuckDB in-process analytical engine.

The middleware is structured around several core engines:

- **Visual Operation Evaluation Engine:** Processes visualization and explainability requests initiated by user interactions with the UI.
- **Visualization Query Optimizer:** Optimizes visualization queries based on both the data characteristics of the dataset and the properties of the requested view (such as visualization

type, screen resolution, selected parameters, and zoom level). It employs techniques such as sampling, aggregation, and adaptive indexing, derived from the scalable visual analytics methods presented in Section 3.4, to minimize response time and enable smooth, interactive exploration.

- **Cache Manager:** Handles data caching and retrieval to minimise latency during exploration. Caching operates both in memory and at the file system level. When users examine an experiment, the system initially loads only metadata describing available inputs and outputs, while data artifacts (for example, test datasets) are not fetched automatically. Instead, they are retrieved on demand when the user selects a specific artifact for visualisation. Most of these artifacts are large files (e.g., CSV, JSON, or Parquet) stored in the Decentralised Data Management system. When a requested file is fetched, it is cached locally on the system hosting the User Interaction Module, allowing subsequent accesses to be served directly from the local cache without repeated network transfers. This mechanism significantly reduces I/O overhead and ensures responsive interaction even for large experimental data. In addition to file-based caching, in-memory caching is also employed to accelerate repeated access to frequently requested elements, such as metric results or experiment metadata retrieved from the Data Access Layer of the ExtremeXP framework. For all data accesses, the Access Control component ensures that only authenticated and authorised users can retrieve the requested datasets.
- **Prefetching Engine:** Designed to anticipate and retrieve data that are likely to be requested in subsequent visual or explainability operations. Its goal is to maintain low latency and ensure seamless user interaction during continuous exploration. Prefetching decisions can be guided by patterns in recent user interactions (such as panning, zooming, or switching between related experiment views) and by metadata describing dependencies between workflows, metrics, and artifacts. For example, when a user examines a specific workflow run and analyses its input data, the system can proactively fetch the corresponding data for related runs so that transitions between them remain instantaneous. This mechanism is particularly important in the ExtremeXP framework, where datasets and artifacts are stored in the Decentralised Data Management (DDM) system, and each access may involve transferring large files across distributed storage nodes. By anticipating such operations, the Prefetching Engine reduces perceived latency and helps sustain smooth, interactive analysis across experiments.

Through this architecture, the middleware ensures that even complex user queries over large-scale experimental data can be answered with low latency, enabling real-time, interactive exploration and explanation of results.

Although the Visualization Middleware has been developed primarily for integration with the ExtremeXP framework, it was designed from the outset to follow a generic and extensible architecture. The middleware is built around an abstract experiment model that defines core entities such as experiments, runs, tasks, metrics, and artifacts. This abstraction allows the User Interaction Module to connect not only to the ExtremeXP Data Abstraction Layer but also to external experiment tracking tools such as MLflow, provided that compatible service implementations are supplied. In addition to the ExtremeXP integration, an MLflow-based implementation has also been developed and demonstrated in [10].

2.2.3 Explainability Module

When explainability insights are requested by the user, the process is coordinated through the **Visual Operation Evaluation Engine**, which delegates the request to the Explainability Module. This module

is responsible for selecting the appropriate method from the **Explainability Methods Repository**, executing it, and returning the results for presentation in the UI. Depending on the method and the data available, this may involve training a surrogate model, applying global techniques such as ALE plots, or generating local explanations such as counterfactuals. The computed explanations are then passed back to the Visual Operation Evaluation Engine and delivered to the UI, where they are integrated into the user's ongoing visual exploration.

2.3 From experiment specifications to visualizations

For the User Interaction Module, the entry point is the **experiment entity**, which is retrieved from the Data Abstraction Layer (DAL). This entity provides the core metadata of the experiment along with references to its workflows, the tasks and metrics for each workflow, and the associated datasets. These elements are progressively queried and visualized as the user explores the experiment.

The Visualization UI includes a **Visualization Metamodel**, which acts as an abstraction layer for generating visualizations. Once an experiment and its associated workflows, tasks, and datasets have been retrieved from the DAL, the information is mapped to this metamodel, which defines how different elements of the experiment model are bound to visualization components. By separating the underlying data structures from the visual components, the metamodel enables the same visualization elements to be applied to different data types and purposes, ensuring both reusability and extensibility.

Based on the characteristics of experiment-related data, the system dynamically determines the most appropriate visualization methods. For example, scalar metrics produced by workflows can be mapped to bar charts for cross-workflow comparison, whereas time series metrics are presented in line charts for more detailed comparison across workflows. This mapping logic is driven by the type of information available in the DAL and, where necessary, by characteristics computed at runtime.

For **input and output datasets**, the system analyses their properties—such as schema, dimensionality, distribution, or spatial/temporal attributes—to determine suitable visualization methods. A dataset with geospatial attributes, for example, can be mapped to interactive maps, while temporal data can be displayed in time series charts. Tabular datasets may be represented through statistical summaries, histograms, or scatterplots. Rich filtering is also enabled based on the specific attributes and characteristics of each dataset.

All these mappings are not hard-coded but are determined dynamically, allowing the User Interaction Module to flexibly adapt visualizations to the properties of the available data.

3 Visualization User Interface

The Visualization User Interface (UI) is a core component of the User Interaction Module, enabling users to monitor, control, and analyse the execution and results of their experiments within the ExtremeXP framework. It provides a unified environment for exploring workflows, inspecting metrics, and visualizing input and output data, supporting interactive, human-in-the-loop experimentation.

The Visualization UI has been implemented as a web-based application using **React** and **Material UI (MUI)** to ensure a consistent, accessible, and responsive design across devices. For data visualization, **Vega-Lite** is employed for declarative charting, while **Leaflet** supports interactive geospatial views that display and overlay location-based or sensor data outputs.

The following subsections describe the main pages and functionalities of the Visualization UI, outlining their purposes and key features.

3.1 Experiment Monitoring Page

The **Figure 2**: Experiment Monitoring Page showing workflow progress, execution table, and parameter–metric visualization. is the main landing view of the Visualization User Interface and provides a comprehensive overview of an experiment’s execution status and outcomes. It combines real-time monitoring, overview comparison, and workflow lifecycle management within a unified interface, enabling users to remain in the loop throughout the experimentation process.

Figure 2: Experiment Monitoring Page showing workflow progress, execution table, and parameter–metric visualization.

At the top of the page, a progress summary bar displays the overall state of the experiment, reporting the number of **Completed**, **Running**, and **Failed** workflows. This visual indicator allows users to quickly assess the experiment’s progress and detect potential execution issues at a glance.

Workflow Execution Table

The central component of the page is the **Workflow Table**, which lists all completed or running workflows (runs). Each row corresponds to a single workflow instance and provides:

- the **Workflow ID** and a concise summary of its variability-point parameters, such as hyperparameter values or task variant selections,
- the recorded **performance metrics**, such as accuracy, loss, or runtime. For time-series metrics captured during execution (for example, accuracy over epochs), the last recorded value is displayed to summarize the workflow’s latest state,
- **action controls** for lifecycle management (**pause**, **resume**, **terminate**), navigation to the **Workflow Details Page**, or **user feedback** through a star-based rating mechanism, allowing experts to provide qualitative evaluations of a workflow’s performance or relevance. Controlling the lifecycle in this way allows users to, for example, terminate long-running workflows or those deemed unpromising based on insights from already completed runs. A

duplication control is also provided, enabling users to clone an existing workflow and adjust its parameters before scheduling it for execution, thereby supporting rapid, insight-driven iteration.

The table supports sorting, filtering, aggregation, and multi-selection to facilitate analytical comparison. Selecting one workflow navigates the user to its **Workflow Analysis Page**, while selecting multiple entries opens the **Comparative Analysis Page** for side-by-side comparison of parameters and metrics.

The Workflow Table also includes an option to **filter by experiment space**. Within the ExtremeXP framework, complex experiments may involve multiple workflow types that differ in parameters, structure, or conditional execution logic. For example, in Use Case 5 (failure prevention in manufacturing), which involves the analysis of machine sensor measurements and the training of classifiers to detect anomalies, an experiment may begin with workflows that train multi-class classifiers to identify not only the presence of an anomaly but also its type (mechanical or electrical). Depending on the evaluation results of this step (e.g., classification accuracy), the system may then trigger a binary classification workflow to refine the analysis and improve detection accuracy. These workflows can have distinct configurations and parameter sets, while intermediate workflows may also appear that do not perform direct data processing but instead serve control or interaction purposes—for instance, coordinating conditional logic within the experiment or explicitly requesting user validation of intermediate results. The experiment-space filter allows users to isolate and examine such subsets independently, providing a clearer overview and supporting more targeted analysis for each workflow type within an experiment.

Scheduled Workflows Tab

A secondary tab labelled **Scheduled** displays workflows that are queued but not yet executed. This view enables interactive scheduling management, allowing users to reorder or remove pending workflows. By linking analytical insights from completed runs with scheduling decisions, the page supports adaptive experimentation, an essential feature for human-in-the-loop operation.

Parallel Coordinates Plot

The lower section of the page hosts a **Parallel Coordinates Plot** that complements the tabular view with a multi-dimensional analytical perspective. Each vertical axis represents a variability parameter, and each workflow is visualized as a polyline connecting its parameter values across axes. Line colour encodes a user-selected performance metric (e.g., accuracy or loss), allowing users to visually identify clusters of high-performing configurations and observe how parameter interactions affect outcomes.

This visualization helps users:

- identify optimal configurations that yield superior performance,
- detect parameter sensitivities and trade-offs between competing metrics and guide to subsequent experimentation by highlighting regions of interest within the parameter space.

3.2 Workflow Analysis Page

The **Workflow Analysis Page** (Figure 3) provides an in-depth view of a single workflow's configuration, structure, execution results, and analytical insights. It enables users to examine workflow parameters, metrics, and artifacts, as well as the internal composition of the workflow into tasks—each with its

own configuration, recorded metrics, and associated inputs or outputs. For workflows that include trained models, the page also supports detailed performance evaluation and explainability analysis. Each workflow page thus serves as a self-contained analytical workspace for post-hoc evaluation and interpretability.

Figure 3: Workflow Analysis Page providing a detailed view of workflow parameters, metrics, and artifacts organized by task, and serving as an entry point for detailed model performance analysis and explainability.

At the top of the page, a header panel summarizes key metadata such as the workflow ID, execution status, and number of tasks completed. Users can also select to view the corresponding **workflow diagram**, providing a visual representation of the workflow structure and task dependencies. Additionally, a rating control (e.g., five-star scale) allows users to provide qualitative feedback alongside quantitative metrics, enabling subjective assessments to be captured and later leveraged for adaptive experimentation and recommendations.

Workflow Details Panel

On the left, a **tree view** organizes workflow components into two main sections: *Workflow Details* and *Model Insights*.

The **Workflow Details** section lists all parameters, metrics, and datasets associated with the workflow, organized hierarchically by the tasks defined in the experiment specification. Selecting an item dynamically updates the main content area with the corresponding visualization or data view:

- **Tasks** – Display detailed information about each task’s execution, including its status, start and end timestamps, and duration, along with the parameter values used during execution, as illustrated in Figure 3. This view allows users to assess individual task performance and identify potential bottlenecks or failed steps.

- **Parameters** – Display the parameter value distribution across workflow runs, helping users identify how variations influence outcomes. The main panel also presents summary statistics such as distinct parameter values and the number of workflows using each configuration.
- **Metrics** – Show the recorded evolution of metrics (e.g., accuracy or loss over epochs) or their final values, depending on the metric type. The main panel includes contextual information such as the capture time within the workflow and aggregate statistics across all runs (mean, min, max).
- **Inputs / Outputs** – Allow inspection of any input or output artifacts used in the workflow. Selecting a dataset activates the **Data Exploration View**, which initially presents a tabular preview. Users can then filter, explore, or generate interactive visualizations such as scatter plots, bar charts, or line charts (Figure 4). Visualization options adapt to dataset characteristics: for instance, datasets with geospatial attributes are displayed on a **map view** (showing points or density overlays, Figure 5), while datasets with both spatial and temporal dimensions enable trajectory visualizations. Unlike traditional experiment tracking tools, where analysis is typically limited to metrics and static plots generated during the experiment execution, this functionality enables **direct visual exploration of the actual input and output data** within the same interface used for analysing metrics and results. This integration fosters a more comprehensive and insight-driven approach to experiment analytics, supporting deeper understanding of model behaviour and data-driven decision-making.

Figure 4: Data Exploration View showing available chart options; a line chart is displayed in this example.

Figure 5: Data Exploration View showing two map-based visualizations: trajectories (bottom) and heatmap-based density overlays (top).

Model Insights Panel

The **Model Insights** section in the tree view is enabled for workflows that include the necessary machine learning artifacts—trained models, test datasets, and ground-truth labels. It provides specialized ML performance visualizations and explainability results. The section is organized around the models trained within the workflow, allowing users to explore each model instance independently.

Selecting a model automatically generates a suite of performance visualizations, including **confusion matrices**, **ROC curves**, and **precision–recall plots** (Figure 6), enabling rapid evaluation of model behaviour and effectiveness.

Figure 6: Model Insights Section showing model performance visualizations

A complementary **Instance View** (Figure 7) presents the test dataset, its predictions, and ground-truth values at the instance level, available in both tabular and scatter-plot formats. Users can select two attributes for direct comparison or use a dimensionality-reduced projection (e.g., UMAP) to inspect clusters, misclassifications, and outliers. Instances can also be filtered by classification outcome (e.g., misclassified samples). For any selected instance, the **Counterfactual Explanations View** (Figure 8) shows the minimal feature changes required to alter the model's prediction, providing actionable insights into decision boundaries and model robustness. An additional tab in this view extends the functionality to the workflow level, suggesting alternative hyperparameter values for the model training task that would likely change the model's prediction outcome (see Section 5.2.2). This feature not only enhances interpretability but also enables **interactive experimentation**: users can directly trigger the creation of a new workflow based on these alternative configurations, effectively closing the loop between explanation and re-execution.

Figure 7: Instance View showing test data, predictions, and ground-truth values.

Figure 8: Counterfactual Explanations View within the Instance View, showing misclassified instances on a scatter plot and their corresponding counterfactuals below.

The **Feature Explainability View** (Figure 9) provides global interpretability results such as Feature Importance, Accumulated Local Effects (ALE), and Partial Dependence Plots (PDP), computed dynamically based on the model type and experiment configuration. Depending on the experiment and analysis context, different explanation types may be displayed to emphasize the most relevant aspects of model behaviour. For example, in *Use Case 1 (Flood Prediction)*, feature importance analyses and gradient-based attribution methods (Integrated Gradients) are used to illustrate how hydrological and environmental variables (such as rainfall, topography (DEM), and water depth inputs) influence the predicted flood probabilities and spatial flood extent.

Additionally, the **Hyperparameter Explainability View** (Figure 10) integrates pipeline-level explainability methods (see Section 5.2), such as ALE and PDP applied to the relationship between model performance and training configurations. These results reveal sensitivity patterns across the hyperparameter space, helping users refine experimental setups or identify more promising parameter ranges for subsequent runs.

All explainability analyses are executed on demand through the Explainability Module and linked to the workflow context, enabling users to interpret model behaviour, assess feature effects, and understand the influence of hyperparameters and pipeline settings within the same interface.

Figure 9: Feature Explainability View showing feature-level effects using feature importance, PDP, ALE plots.

Figure 10: Hyperparameter Explainability View providing insights into relationships between training configurations and model performance

3.3 Comparative Analysis Page

The **Comparative Analysis Page** enables side-by-side evaluation of multiple workflows, allowing users to analyse how different configurations, parameters, or data inputs affect performance and behaviour. It builds upon the experiment overview functionality by offering a dedicated workspace for more in depth comparative visual analysis across selected workflows.

Users can access this page by selecting multiple completed workflows from the **Experiment Monitoring Page** and click on the “Compare Selected workflows” button or clicking on the *Comparative Analysis* tab. The page retains a compact version of the Workflow Table on the left, enabling filtering, grouping, and selection refinement, while the right side presents a set of analytical tabs for detailed comparison. The Comparative Analysis Page consists of three primary analytical tabs: **Metrics**, **Model Insights**, and **Data**.

Metrics Tab

The **Metrics Tab** (Figure 11) provides a quantitative comparison of key performance metrics across the selected workflows. Single-value metrics are displayed as bar charts, allowing direct side-by-side comparison of results (for example, accuracy, recall, or AUC). Series metrics—such as learning curves over epochs or training steps—are visualized as line charts, where each line corresponds to one of the selected workflows. These views help users quickly identify performance trends, outliers, or trade-offs across workflows, making it easier to assess which configurations or parameter settings led to superior results.

The tab also supports grouping and aggregation based on selected variability points (e.g., hyperparameter values or task variants). Workflows sharing common settings can be grouped, and aggregated statistics (such as average accuracy or loss per group) are computed and visualized accordingly. This enables both fine-grained comparisons of individual runs and high-level analyses of systematic effects caused by parameter changes or experimental conditions.

Figure 11: Workflow Comparison Page showing the Metrics Tab for quantitative comparison of performance across workflows.

Model Insights Tab

The **Model Insights Tab** (Figure 12) extends the comparison to a deeper, behavioural level by examining model diagnostics and instance-level predictions. It provides multiple analysis modes accessible via buttons at the top of the tab: **Confusion Matrix**, **ROC Curve**, and **Instance View**.

- **Confusion Matrix View** displays per-class performance for each workflow, highlighting where models make similar or diverging misclassifications.
- **ROC Curve View** visualizes trade-offs between true and false positive rates across workflows, allowing direct comparison of model discriminative power.
- **Instance View** (Figure 13) provides a detailed, instance-level comparison of predictions and ground-truth values. Each chart corresponds to one workflow, plotting user-selected feature pairs or system-suggested attributes. Points are color-coded according to predicted versus actual classes, enabling intuitive inspection of classification boundaries and misclassifications.

The “*Misclassified*” toggle allows users to highlight incorrectly predicted samples, making it easy to identify whether models fail on the same instances or in different regions of the feature space. Together, these tools provide a bridge between high-level metrics and model behaviour, enabling researchers to understand *why* certain workflows perform differently—whether due to decision boundary shape, class imbalance, or data-specific biases.

Figure 12: Workflow Comparison Page - Model Insights Tab displaying confusion matrices for selected workflows.

Figure 13: Instance View within the Model Insights Tab showing per-instance prediction comparisons across workflows.

Data Tab

The **Data Tab** (Figure 14) provides a comparative view of the datasets used or produced across workflows in an experiment. This view is particularly useful when workflows are executed on different versions of the training or test data, or when data transformations are applied within each workflow.

Users can select a dataset, and the interface automatically renders **small-multiple histograms**, one per feature or column. Each plot displays the **binned value distribution** of that feature for every selected workflow, allowing users to quickly detect differences in data distributions across runs.

These visual comparisons help users understand how variations in input data may influence performance and can also reveal issues that affect experiment validity—such as **data drift**, **sampling inconsistencies**, or **pipeline-induced skews**. For instance, noticeable shifts in feature distributions may point to changes in preprocessing steps or data selection strategies between workflows.

Figure 14: The Data Tab presents side-by-side visualizations of dataset features across workflows, offering an overview of data characteristics for comparative analysis.

3.4 Human in the loop tasks in ExtremeXP

A central principle of the ExtremeXP framework is to maintain the human in the loop throughout the experimentation lifecycle. Beyond automated execution and analysis, ExtremeXP enables users to monitor, interpret, and intervene during experimentation, ensuring that exploration remains both data-driven and human-guided. This approach allows expert knowledge to steer and validate decisions at key stages—from experiment design and execution to post-hoc analysis and explainability. Within the framework, the User Interaction Module serves as the primary interface for these interactions. After defining experiments through the Domain-Specific Language (DSL), providing the code for the various tasks, and initiating execution, users can monitor progress, compare alternative workflows, evaluate results, and derive insights that inform subsequent experimentation.

This iterative cycle—specify, observe, analyse, and interpret, refine—embodies the human-in-the-loop experimentation paradigm. It aligns with the four modes of interaction proposed by Chromik & Butz [5], which describe how human insight and system automation co-evolve to drive continuous improvement in experimental outcomes. Several human-in-the-loop mechanisms have already been implicitly described in the previous sections presenting the visualization pages. In this section, we bring these interaction modes together in a unified context to highlight their role across the experimentation lifecycle and introduce an additional form of interaction—the **Custom Interactive Human-in-the-Loop Tasks**, which embed user feedback directly within the workflow execution process.

Experiment Monitoring and Control

Human interaction begins during **experiment execution**. Through the *Experiment Monitoring Page*, users can observe the real-time progress of workflows, inspect their status, and manage their lifecycle by pausing, resuming, or terminating specific runs—or even the entire experiment. They can also reorder or remove scheduled workflows, dynamically adjusting execution priorities based on partial results or emerging insights from completed runs. This represents **operational oversight**, allowing

users to guide experiment scheduling and resource allocation while maintaining automation efficiency.

Explorative Visualization and Analysis

Once results are available, users engage in explorative analysis through the **Visualization and Comparison Pages**. These interfaces allow them to examine datasets, metrics, and artifacts interactively—filtering, sorting, and visualizing outputs to uncover trends, correlations, and anomalies. Users can compare alternative workflows or model configurations side by side, assessing trade-offs between performance metrics and identifying promising directions for further experimentation. This stage supports *insight generation* and bridges raw data with human interpretation, enabling experts to translate analytical results into actionable knowledge.

Explainability-Driven Interpretation

Through the integrated **Explainability Module**, users gain a deeper understanding of model and ML pipeline behaviour. By visualizing feature attributions, hyperparameter effects, and counterfactual scenarios, users can validate whether model decisions align with domain expectations and explore how modifications might improve performance or fairness. These explainability insights strengthen transparency and trust in the analytical process and guide the design of subsequent experiments.

User Ratings and Feedback Collection

In addition to direct interaction, ExtremeXP captures explicit user feedback through rating mechanisms embedded in the Visualization UI. After analysing experiment results, metrics, or explanations, users can rate individual workflows or models based on their perceived quality and relevance. These ratings are stored as part of the experiment's metadata, allowing users to track their evaluation history and compare subjective assessments with objective performance metrics.

Custom Interactive Human-in-the-Loop Tasks

Beyond the forms of interaction described above, ExtremeXP also supports *runtime human participation* directly within the workflow execution process through **Interactive Human-in-the-Loop Tasks**. Defined in the experiment DSL and accompanied by custom UI code, these tasks act as **pause-and-resume points** in the pipeline, invoking a web interface that collects user feedback to guide subsequent execution. Such tasks can be defined either at the **experiment level** or at the **workflow level**.

At the **experiment level**, an interactive workflow is executed that has access to results from previously completed workflows and requires user feedback to determine the next execution steps. At the **workflow level**, an interactive task is embedded within the workflow itself, requiring explicit user input before execution can proceed.

Each interactive task is fully specified within the DSL, including the definition of the expected input structure and the accompanying UI code that determines how information is presented to the user. At runtime, when execution reaches such a task, the pipeline **pauses** and dynamically deploys a lightweight web server that exposes standard REST endpoints for data exchange and serves the corresponding web interface. This interface is **embedded directly within the Visualization UI** as an iframe, providing a seamless interaction experience. When a workflow reaches an interactive task, it is displayed as *pending* in the monitoring interface, with a visual indicator prompting the user to

provide the required feedback. Once the user submits the input, the feedback is processed through the exposed API, and the workflow **resumes execution**, taking this input into account.

A representative example of such functionality is found in Use Case 5 (Failure Prevention in Manufacturing). In this scenario, the experiment involves both multi-class and binary classification model training along with their corresponding evaluation tasks. An evaluation phase ranks the trained models based on performance metrics (e.g., accuracy). If the best multi-class model exceeds a predefined performance threshold, it proceeds; otherwise, the system dynamically switches to the best-performing binary classification model. Following this automated selection, an Interactive Human-in-the-Loop Task is triggered to incorporate expert supervision (Figure 15). Domain experts are prompted to review the anomaly predictions and validate their correctness, effectively bridging automated learning with human expertise. At runtime, relevant datasets and artifacts are retrieved dynamically from the Decentralised Data Management (DDM) system, ensuring that experts interact with the corresponding, up-to-date outputs. Feedback collected during this interaction is stored either as output data within the DDM or as user-defined metrics in the Data Abstraction Layer (DAL), making it accessible for subsequent visualization and traceability. This mechanism ensures that **human validation becomes an integral and traceable part of the experimentation lifecycle**, linking automated analytics with expert decision-making and reinforcing the reliability and trustworthiness of ExtremeXP results.

Figure 15 Example of a custom interactive Human-in-the-Loop task interface embedded in the Visualization UI, enabling expert validation during workflow execution.

4 Techniques for Scalable Interactive Visual Exploration

This section outlines the research work carried out to support the interactive visual analysis of large datasets within the ExtremeXP framework. The methods developed in this context aim to address the challenges of efficiently exploring and analysing high-volume data while maintaining interactive performance. These efforts complement the broader goals of the User Interaction Module by providing computational foundations for scalable, low-latency visual analytics.

The core motivation behind this work is that users often need to explore and analyse large datasets directly, without lengthy preprocessing steps such as importing data into databases or performing full indexing. This need is particularly evident in experiment analytics, where datasets used as inputs (e.g., training or test data) or generated as outputs (e.g., prediction results) are frequently stored in file-based formats such as CSV. When these files reach substantial sizes, conventional methods struggle to deliver responsive interaction without additional database or preprocessing layers.

The objective is therefore to minimize the time from data availability to analysis, offering fast, approximate insights while maintaining acceptable accuracy for visual exploration. In many exploratory scenarios, interactive response time is more critical than exact precision. To this end, we have investigated and prototyped data structures and algorithms that enable real-time, interactive visual analysis of large datasets with controllable accuracy guarantees.

The research focuses on three complementary directions:

1. Adaptive indexing of raw data files, supporting interactive two-dimensional exploration (e.g., map-based visualizations) and approximate aggregate analytics without requiring full data loading or indexing.
2. Adaptive caching strategies for time-series data, enabling error-bounded line chart visualizations while reducing data access latency.
3. Sketch-based pattern search over cached time series data representations, integrating interactive visualization and slope-based temporal pattern discovery within a unified sketching framework.

Together, these methods form a scalable analytics foundation that supports responsive and reliable interaction with large datasets. They are aligned with the goals of the User Interaction Module to enhance its human-in-the-loop experimentation capabilities at scale.

4.1 Adaptive Indexing for Approximate Query Answering in 2D Visual Exploration

This section presents an adaptive indexing approach for interactive visual analysis over large raw datasets (e.g., CSV) using 2D visualization techniques such as maps or scatterplots. The method enables users to examine individual data objects and compute aggregate values for the elements contained within the currently visualized window of the 2D exploration view, while addressing the high I/O and parsing costs associated with large file-based datasets that often hinder interactivity. Users interact with visualization through operations such as pan and zoom, which dynamically update both the displayed aggregates and the corresponding spatial or attribute-based data view.

The overall objective is to minimize data-to-analysis time while maintaining real-time responsiveness during exploration. In many scenarios, large datasets are stored in raw formats rather than databases, which would normally require lengthy preprocessing or indexing phases before analysis can begin. To overcome this limitation, in-situ exploration techniques operate directly on raw files, while adaptive indexing methods build and refine index structures incrementally as users navigate through the data.

While such adaptive indexing ensures low initialization cost, performance may still degrade in dense regions or during early queries where the index has not yet adapted. At the same time, users in exploratory visual analysis often value responsiveness over exact precision—approximate results are sufficient to reveal trends and anomalies, while detailed computation can follow in later stages.

To support this trade-off, we propose a method that integrates adaptive indexing with incremental sampling, combining the low-latency benefits of in-situ exploration with the statistical guarantees of Approximate Query Processing (AQP). Earlier reporting on this work appeared in the *M18 Interim Activity and Management Report (Appendix I)* and in a preliminary study presented in [11], which introduced an initial approach in this direction. While the initial version demonstrated promising

results, it was based on deterministic aggregate bounds, which limited its flexibility for attributes with high variability. The current version builds on that foundation by integrating incremental sampling with adaptive indexing, enabling statistically controlled approximations and improved scalability for interactive visual analytics over large raw datasets. The extended study has been submitted for journal publication.

Background and Exploration Model

The proposed method operates in an *in-situ* visual exploration setting, where users interactively analyse data directly from large CSV files without prior loading into a database. Each file contains multidimensional data objects described by numeric or spatial attributes, two of which (e.g., longitude and latitude) define the axes of the visualization, while the remaining attributes represent the values used for analytical computation (e.g., mean, sum, count).

Users interact with the system through operations such as *pan* and *zoom*, which dynamically adjust the visualized area (viewport) and trigger queries to retrieve or aggregate objects whose attribute values fall within the displayed window. As exploration continues, the system refines its internal structures to improve query efficiency while maintaining real-time response times.

Our proposed method builds upon the VALINOR indexing scheme [12], a hierarchical, tile-based adaptive index designed for in-memory exploration of large raw data files. VALINOR organizes data into rectangular tiles over the domains of two selected axis attributes and maintains aggregate metadata (e.g., count, sum) for each tile. During interaction, the index adapts by subdividing frequently accessed tiles, thereby aligning its structure with user exploration patterns. While this approach offers interactive performance, its reliance on exact aggregates results in high I/O cost, particularly for dense regions or attributes not yet indexed. The method presented here extends this foundation with incremental sampling and approximate aggregate computation, allowing statistically bounded accuracy while reducing redundant file access and ensuring scalability for interactive visual analytics.

Index Structure and Query Model

The proposed method introduces **VALINOR-A**, an extension of VALINOR designed to support interactive, error-bounded exploration of large raw datasets. VALINOR-A adds new capabilities for **incremental sampling**, and **approximate aggregate computation with confidence guarantees**.

The index operates in the context of **2D visual exploration**, where users analyse data stored in **large CSV files** through visualizations such as maps or scatterplots. Each user interaction—such as panning or zooming—defines a **spatial query** over the currently visualized region. These exploratory queries specify (i) the area of interest, (ii) the aggregates to compute (e.g., mean, sum, count) on **one or more attributes other than the two used for the 2D exploration**, and (iii) a **user-defined accuracy constraint** expressed as a maximum relative error and a confidence level. This mechanism enables users to balance responsiveness and accuracy, requesting coarser approximations during overview analysis and tighter bounds for detailed inspection.

Internally, VALINOR-A organizes the data space into a **hierarchy of non-overlapping tiles** defined over the two axis attributes (for example, latitude and longitude). Each tile maintains **metadata representing statistical aggregates** for other numeric attributes of the enclosed objects. Unlike the original VALINOR index, which computed exact aggregates for every tile, VALINOR-A stores **approximate metadata** derived from incrementally collected samples. A lightweight **bitmap structure** records which objects have already been sampled, allowing the system to refine aggregates as needed without redundant file reads.

An illustrative example of the VALINOR-A index structure is shown in Figure 16, depicting how data objects are organized into tiles and how each tile maintains aggregate metadata and sampling information.

Figure 16: Example of the VALINOR-A index structure. (a) Raw data objects with their attributes and file offsets; (b) hierarchical tiling of the data space; (c) detailed view of a tile containing approximate metadata, sampled objects, and a bitmap indicating sampled entries.

Tiles can therefore exist in three states:

1. **Exact**, when all enclosed objects have been processed and full aggregates are available;
2. **Approximate**, when aggregates are computed from partial samples; and
3. **Unavailable** when no data has yet been sampled.

The **initialization phase** of the index follows the *in-situ* paradigm: the index is created dynamically when the first query is issued, avoiding the need for an explicit preprocessing step. A coarse grid of tiles is initialized by scanning the raw file once and computing summary statistics for each tile. As the user continues to explore, the index adaptively refines the regions that receive more attention, progressively optimizing performance where it matters most.

Approximate Query Processing and Index Adaptation

When a user explores the dataset through 2D interactions such as panning or zooming, a query is issued over **VALINOR-A**. The query engine identifies the tiles overlapping the current viewport and evaluates how much of their existing metadata can be reused. Each tile is characterized by (i) its spatial relation to the viewport—fully or partially contained—and (ii) the status of its stored metadata: exact, approximate, or unavailable.

Based on these properties, VALINOR-A determines whether a tile can be used as is or requires additional sampling from the raw data. The main cases are:

- **Fully contained, exact tiles:** existing aggregates are used directly with no additional file access.
- **Fully contained, approximate tiles:** aggregates are reused unless their uncertainty exceeds the user-defined error bound, in which case incremental sampling refines them.
- **Partially contained tiles:** only the subset of objects within the visible portion is sampled to compute local aggregates.
- **Newly created tiles:** metadata are initialized through targeted sampling as part of the adaptive refinement process.

Sampling is performed incrementally, guided by the current accuracy of results. VALINOR-A dynamically adjusts the sampling rate based on the ratio between the current and target error,

avoiding unnecessary data reads while ensuring that the computed estimates meet the desired confidence interval. Newly sampled objects are incorporated into the index immediately: for fully contained tiles, updated metadata remain valid for future queries, while for partially contained tiles, sampled values are used only for the current query to preserve uniformity guarantees. Each query result integrates **exact** and **approximate** contributions from the relevant tiles, producing the aggregate values for the requested attributes along with a confidence interval at the specified confidence level. Exact tiles contribute deterministic values, while uncertainty originates only from tiles with sampled or incomplete metadata.

The same process that governs query evaluation also drives **index adaptation**. As users repeatedly explore specific regions, VALINOR-A automatically refines the index by subdividing tiles in areas of high activity. This fine-grained adaptation increases the number of fully contained tiles with available metadata, thus reducing I/O requirements for future queries. The decision to split tiles is guided by an expected I/O-benefit heuristic and typically follows a quadtree-like strategy, though alternative partitioning schemes are supported.

Together, the integration of approximate query processing and adaptive indexing enables **user-driven, error-bounded exploration** over large raw datasets. VALINOR-A eliminates the need for expensive preprocessing or data loading into databases, offering a scalable and efficient approach for real-time visual analytics. As users interact with the system, VALINOR-A continuously improves its internal state—reducing latency, stabilizing response times, and ensuring smooth human-in-the-loop exploration even on commodity hardware.

Performance Evaluation

VALINOR-A was experimentally evaluated to assess its responsiveness, scalability, and approximation reliability in interactive exploration scenarios. The method was tested on both synthetic datasets (11–51 GB) and a real dataset (the 26 GB NYC Taxi Trips) emulating typical 2D exploration workflows with sequential pan and zoom interactions. Competing methods included the original VALINOR, which performs exact computation, and a sampling-only baseline (VALINOR-S) that executes incremental sampling without adaptive metadata reuse. VALINOR-A consistently outperforms the baseline methods. It achieves between four- and eight-fold speedups in query execution time compared to both exact computation and sampling-only baselines, while maintaining interactive response times—typically under one second—even for strict 1 % error bounds. These findings confirm that VALINOR-A effectively combines low-latency in-situ query processing with statistically controlled approximations, providing a scalable mechanism for real-time exploration of large raw datasets.

Figure 17 illustrates the impact of the user-defined error bound on overall query execution time across the emulated 2D exploration scenario. As expected, looser error bounds lead to faster execution for both VALINOR-A and VALINOR-S (sampling-only), while the original VALINOR, which performs exact computations, exhibits consistently higher and constant execution times across all settings, as it does not vary with the error bound. As the accuracy constraints tighten, VALINOR-A scales much more efficiently than VALINOR-S, showing only a modest increase in query time by comparison. This demonstrates the system’s ability to balance accuracy and interactivity, allowing users to control the trade-off between latency and precision during visual exploration.

Figure 17: Impact of user-defined error bound on total query time.

4.2 Visualization-aware Time-Series Caching

This section focuses on methods for the interactive visual exploration of large time-series datasets, particularly relevant to UC5 (failure prevention in manufacturing), which involves the analysis of continuous machine sensor measurements. Our work on adaptive caching for approximate time-series visualization with accuracy guarantees provides the foundation for scalable, low-latency visualization in such contexts.

The interactive visual analysis of large time-series datasets poses significant challenges due to their high volume and continuity, requiring visualization methods that remain both responsive and accurate. Traditional techniques such as aggregation or sampling can reduce latency but often distort visual patterns, undermining reliability for tasks such as anomaly detection or correlation analysis. To address this, visualization-aware aggregation methods [13] align data aggregation with the visualization’s resolution, grouping values into pixel-wide intervals and computing min, max, first, and last aggregates to ensure visually accurate results. However, such methods incur high latency during interactive operations (e.g., panning or zooming), since overlapping intervals must be repeatedly re-fetched and re-aggregated, preventing efficient reuse of previous computations.

To address these limitations, our work on visualization aware time series caching approach, named MinMaxCache [14], enables users to explore time-series data interactively through line charts and operations such as panning across time intervals or zooming in and out at varying resolutions. The method fetches data from the underlying data store—whether a relational database (e.g., SQL-based), a time-series database (e.g., InfluxDB), or file-based storage (e.g., CSV or Parquet)—at dynamically determined granularities considering visualization parameters and accuracy constraints. Retrieved aggregates are stored in interval trees, allowing efficient reuse across interactions while maintaining accuracy guarantees for the rendered visualization, in terms of correctly rendered pixels relative to the visualization that would be produced using all raw data points. Multiple time-series datasets are managed independently through separate interval trees, each indexed via a hash table for fast access and retrieval.

Min-Max Aggregation with Mid-Interval Timestamps: The aggregation strategy we employ, named Min-Max Aggregation with Mid-Interval Timestamps, aims to decrease the number of data points required for fetching and visualization. It groups the data points into intervals that are smaller than the width of a pixel column and retrieves and caches the min and max values of the y-variable for each group. Instead of using the original timestamps, this strategy arbitrarily assigns the middle of the group’s interval as a timestamp to these two values. This min-max strategy enhances the efficiency of queries, although it could introduce errors into the visualization. However, the aggregates fetched can determine an upper bound for the errors in pixels. Our approach focuses on potential errors in the

visualization domain, specifically computing the maximum number of pixel errors in the visualization generated with MinMaxCache.

Cache Metadata: A node in the tree effectively corresponds to a grouping of a subseries of the time series. Each node stores the following metadata:

- The unique identifier of the time series interval tree to which the node belongs.
- The start and end timestamps of the grouping.
- The aggregation interval, i.e., the length of each time interval in the grouping.
- The variables included in the grouping.
- An array associated with each variable in the grouping that stores the min and max values for each interval corresponding to its specific variable.

Query Evaluation over MinMaxCache:

Figure 18: Query Evaluation over MinMaxCache. illustrates the evaluation of a query over MinMaxCache to generate a visualization with 3 pixels. The process involves the following steps: the evaluation of the query on the cached data (Step 1); the evaluation of the error bound based on the cached data and fetching of missing data (Step 2); the final evaluation of the error and visualization of the results (Step 3).

Figure 18: Query Evaluation over MinMaxCache.

In Step 1, the interval trees that match the requested datasets are identified via their unique identifiers. If a dataset has not been visualized before, a new interval tree is constructed. The cached groupings that overlap with the query time interval are then identified in the interval trees.

Step 2 concerns the evaluation of the error bound. If the cache does not hold data for the entire query interval, the complete query interval is fetched using a default initial parameter value for the data granularity. This effectively sets the number of groups for the interval to be a multiple of the number of pixels of the visualization width. If there is overlapping data, we distinguish three cases: i) The cache holds data for the entire query interval across all variables. We compute a separate error bound for each variable. If errors are within the constraints of each variable, we compute the min-max values of each pixel column based on the contained groupings and visualize the results. We consider this case as *complete cache hit*; for space reasons, this type of query is not shown in the figure. ii) The cache misses data for parts of the query interval of a variable. Again, we compute the error bound based on the groupings overlapping the query interval. If it is within the expected limit (e.g., $< 5\%$) we only fetch the missing part of the query from the datastore. This is a *partial cache hit* (Step 2a). Fetched data is aggregated into new groupings in their corresponding interval trees. In the example, the new grouping

G3 is cached into the variable's tree and used for computing the min-max values of pixel column 3. iii) Finally, if the partial or complete error bounds exceed constraints, we fetch data for the entire query interval, employing a smaller aggregation interval which hopefully reduces the error. This case is a *cache miss*.

After the query is executed and the new groupings are cached, *Step 3* concerns the evaluation of the total error bound considering the new data fetched. If the re-evaluation still exceeds the error bound for some variables, a final M4 query guarantees 100% accurate visualization. Although this can result in increased total query time, our experiments indicate that this occurs in less than 5% of the queries.

Support for CSV-Based Time Series: MinMaxCache was initially designed for database-stored time-series data (e.g., SQL-based, or time-series databases such as InfluxDB), where queries could efficiently retrieve specific temporal ranges through standard query interfaces. However, many real-world scenarios—such as those in UC5—involve time-series data stored in CSV files rather than databases. CSV storage presents unique challenges, including sequential access patterns and the need for careful file offset management to avoid loading entire datasets into memory or performing costly preprocessing steps to import the data into a database.

To address these challenges, we extended the caching approach to support CSV-based time-series storage by implementing file-aware caching mechanisms that maintain file offset pointers at the level of cached time-series intervals (i.e., the start of each interval) for efficient random access. The extended architecture supports both single-file and multi-file scenarios, where each file corresponds to a distinct time series—an arrangement common in industrial environments.

For this mechanism to operate effectively, we assume that data points in each file are sorted by timestamp, which is typically the case in practice. For single CSV files, the cache maintains metadata that maps byte offsets to the start positions of specific time intervals, enabling selective data retrieval without full file scanning. In the multi-file scenario, a unified hash table coordinates cross-file access, ensuring consistent query execution.

The query executor uses these cached offsets whenever they are available. For previously unseen time ranges, it estimates the expected byte offset based on the file's sampling rate, timestamp ordering, and nearby cached offsets. The executor then performs targeted random access to the estimated position and scans forward or backward to precisely locate the temporal boundaries of interest. Once identified, these new offsets are added to the cache for reuse in future queries.

This hybrid strategy—combining cached offsets with predictive estimation—minimizes file reading and parsing overhead compared to full sequential scans, as only the relevant portions of each file are accessed. The approach is particularly effective for regularly sampled measurement data, where timestamps are uniformly spaced and offsets can be accurately interpolated from prior cache entries. This design is highly relevant to UC5's manufacturing use case, where high-frequency machine sensor data is periodically stored in separate CSV files representing individual machine cycles.

Interactive Benchmarking: To allow for the interactive evaluation of the performance of MinMaxCache, in addition to the extensive experimental results presented in [14] (which demonstrate up to 10× speedup over non-cached methods while maintaining pixel-level error bounds), we developed TimeVizBench [15], an interactive benchmarking environment for scalable time-series visualization methods. Unlike conventional benchmarking tools that execute predefined test suites, TimeVizBench enables users to interactively explore large time-series datasets while monitoring latency, throughput, and accuracy metrics in real time. This allows side-by-side comparison of different such scalable visualization techniques (e.g., MinMaxCache, M4) under realistic exploration scenarios, reflecting how users actually interact with data during analysis. The platform thus bridges

evaluation and exploration, providing both a research testbed and a demonstrator for interactive performance assessment within the ExtremeXP framework.

TimeVizBench provides a comprehensive user interface² comprising three main components. The UI is illustrated in Figure 19. The Configuration Panel (A) allows users to select datasets, specify time ranges and measures for visualization, and configure multiple method instances with both initialization and query-time parameters. The Visualization Panel (B) displays synchronized time series line charts for all configured methods, enabling direct visual comparison with support for interactive pan and zoom operations that update all charts simultaneously. The Performance Metrics Panel (C) presents detailed performance insights through both table and chart views, breaking down query execution into its constituent parts (query time, network time, rendering time) and displaying data retrieval counts for each method. The platform also includes a Quality Measure feature that overlays an error-free reference series on each chart and displays the corresponding SSIM score for accuracy comparison. Users can also download their exploration data, enabling post-hoc analysis and insight extraction.

Figure 19: TimeVizBench User Interface for the interactive benchmarking of methods for large-scale time series exploration.

4.3 Time-Series Caching for Scalable Interactive Visualization and Pattern Search

Building on MinMaxCache, we further developed **SkeTSCache**, a unified multi-level sketch framework that extends our caching approach to support not only interactive visualization but also slope-based pattern search from a single cached representation. While MinMaxCache focused on enabling efficient pan and zoom operations time series stored in databases, SkeTSCache addresses the broader need of integrating interactive pattern search and visualization, particularly relevant for UC5 where operators need to identify anomalies and label data based on visual characteristics. Figure 20 illustrates the system architecture of SkeTSCache. A user poses either visualization or pattern queries. The system routes each query type to its dedicated processor, which reconstructs approximate series from cached aggregates, computes error bounds, and executes the appropriate rendering or matching algorithm. Both processors access a shared cache managed by the Cache Manager, which maintains the interval tree structure. The Cache Manager is responsible for maintaining the interval tree, handling eviction

² <https://timevizbench.imsi.athenarc.gr>

policies based on access patterns and exploration context and coordinating data fetches from the external Time Series Data Store when cached aggregates provide insufficient coverage or granularity.

Figure 20: System Overview for SkeTSCache. A user issues a visualization or a pattern query. Each query is processed separately but utilizes the same cached data; managed by the Cache Manager.

Query Language and Pattern Specifications: SkeTSCache supports an expressive query language for segment-based pattern specifications with temporal and slope constraints. Pattern queries are expressed in calendar time units and specified as sequences of segment specifications, where each segment has duration constraints (in time units) and slope angle ranges. The framework incorporates repetition operators (Kleene star, ranges) that mirror regular expression constructs, enabling complex pattern expressions such as finding sequences with 1-2 upward segments followed by zero or more downward segments. Pattern queries are defined at calendar-aligned time units (second, minute, hour, day), allowing operators to express queries like "find patterns at the hourly level where temperature increases for 2-3 hours followed by a sharp decline". The system evaluates patterns through NFA-based matching over reconstructed sketch series, supporting variable-length patterns and multi-granularity queries without reprocessing the underlying data.

Sketch Structure and Calendar-Aligned Aggregation: SkeTSCache utilizes the same strategy as MinMaxCache, grouping data points into intervals that are smaller than requested (pixel column for visualization and time unit for patterns), and retrieves sketched values for these intervals. SkeTSCache employs calendar-aligned aggregation intervals that correspond to semantically meaningful time units. These intervals can be standard calendar units (e.g., second, minute, hour, day) or integer multiples thereof, provided they divide evenly into a coarser unit. For example, 2-minute, 5-minute, or 15-minute intervals are admissible because they can be rolled up into the next calendar unit (1 hour); similarly, 6-hour or 12-hour intervals roll up into 1 day. This alignment enables exact pattern matching at specified time units while supporting error-bounded visualization by utilizing the method used by MinMaxCache.

Caching Modes and Slope Computation Methods: The framework supports multiple caching modes that balance memory consumption against query capabilities. Complete modes store full statistics: First/Last (FL) mode caches first, last, min, max with timestamps enabling exact slope computation, while Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) mode stores complete regression statistics (sum, sum of x , sum of y , sum of x^2 , count, along with min-max) that merge associatively via component-wise summation. Reduced modes minimize storage: Reduced FL stores first/last measures without timestamps assuming regular sampling, while min-max mode stores only minimal extrema sufficient for visualization. SkeTSCache employs two complementary slope computation methods that work with these caching modes: FirstLast slopes using boundary points for exact transitions, and OLS regression slopes that use summation statistics for robustness to noise and amplitude variations. When cached aggregates contain only min-max values, the system applies an adaptive approximation strategy to compute slope estimates, similar to the one utilized for visualization queries.

Performance Evaluation: We evaluated SkeTSCache on real-world datasets (MNF with 42 million points, INTL with 167 million points, SOCC with 255 million points) using a Guided Search workload

where users alternate between visual operations and pattern queries targeting regions 4-8 zoom levels deeper than the current viewport.

Figure 21 illustrates the comparison of SkeTSCache using different sketch modes against traditional architectures maintaining separate data structures for visualization and pattern search with First/Last slopes. M4-NoC does not use a cache; performing M4 aggregation for visualization and fetching the first/last data points per time-unit interval for pattern search, evaluating them using the NFA we designed. MinMaxCache, is the original method for visualization, that performs separate first/last data point fetching for pattern search, again using the NFA to evaluate the pattern query. M4-C is a SkeTSCache variant that caches first, last, min, max data points. $M4^{\infty}$ -C, caches first, last, min, max values without their timestamps—approximating pattern search using the intervals instead of the real timestamps—and finally $M2^{\infty}$ -C, stores only min, max values, approximating both visualization and pattern search.

From all SkeTSCache variants, $M4^{\infty}$ -C is the most balanced, delivering the lowest median execution time with a tight interquartile range and minimal outliers. In contrast, MinMaxCache, suffers from heavy-tail latency spikes when switching between visualization and pattern operations. M4-NoC, exhibits even worse performance with median times around 1-2 seconds and frequent outliers exceeding 6-8 seconds due to repeated raw data access.

We also evaluated pattern search accuracy using First/Last slope computation across all three datasets. Table 1 presents the results for the SkeTSCache approximate methods. $M2^{\infty}$ -C, which approximates slopes from only min-max values, exhibits catastrophic failure on the noisy INTL dataset with precision of 0.125, recall of 0.012, and F1 score of 0.022. On cleaner datasets (MNF and SOCC), $M2^{\infty}$ -C achieves acceptable but degraded performance with F1 scores of 0.84 and 0.828 respectively, showing precision above 0.9 but recall dropping to 0.793 and 0.769. In contrast, all variants that cache first/last values ($M4^{\infty}$ -C, M4-C, MinMaxCache) achieve perfect pattern detection with precision, recall, and F1 scores of 1.0 across all three datasets. These results demonstrate that while $M2^{\infty}$ -C offers the smallest memory footprint and execution times, it may require more noise-tolerant slope computation methods like OLS regression rather than First/Last for robust pattern matching on real-world sensor data.

Figure 21: Execution time distribution comparison of SkeTSCache variants and baseline methods across INTL, MNF, and SOCC datasets. $M4^{\infty}$ -C achieves the lowest median execution time with minimal outliers, while separate-backend approaches (MinMaxCache, M4-NoC) suffer from heavy-tail latency spikes.

Table 1: Pattern search accuracy metrics using First/Last slope computation across three real-world datasets, for the SkeTSCache approximate variants.

Dataset	Sketch Variant	Precision	Recall	F1
INTL	M2 [∞] -C	0.125	0.012	0.022
INTL	M4 [∞] -C	1.000	1.000	1.000
MNF	M2 [∞] -C	0.918	0.793	0.840
MNF	M4 [∞] -C	1.000	1.000	1.000
SOCC	M2 [∞] -C	0.948	0.769	0.828
SOCC	M4 [∞] -C	1.000	1.000	1.000

5 Explainability Module

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) refers to a set of methods and tools designed to make the behaviour and decisions of machine learning (ML) systems transparent and interpretable to humans. Its goal is to increase the trustworthiness and accountability of AI systems by clarifying how and why specific outcomes are produced.

The **Explainability Module** component, developed as part of Task 4.2, is designed to enhance the transparency and trustworthiness of the experimental process within the ExtremeXP framework. It extends several established explainability algorithms, such as Partial Dependence Plots (PDP), Accumulated Local Effects Plots (ALE), and Counterfactual Explanations, to generate insights not only for the input features of the datasets but also for the hyperparameters of the various machine learning models used throughout the workflows of an experiment.

The module supports two complementary perspectives:

- **Model Explainability**, which explains how input features influence a trained model's predictions.
- **Pipeline Explainability**, which explains how configuration choices (hyperparameters and preprocessing steps) affect performance across workflows.

The Explainability Module communicates via the Visualization Middleware, which mediates all data access and execution requests from the Visualization UI.

Section 5.1 ML model explainability, describing the supported methods along with more specialized techniques such as global counterfactual and spatial attribution methods. **Section 5.2** on pipeline-level explainability, outlining our work on explaining hyperparameter effects and generating counterfactual

pipeline configurations. **Section 5.3** provides some details on the implementation of the Explainability Module, its integration with the Visualization Middleware and UI, as well as helper DSL-level tasks that support the storage and management of artifacts required for explainability workflows.

5.1 ML Model Explainability

ML Model Explainability aims to interpret the significance and impact of individual features and their values within a machine learning model. The primary goal of this process is to provide users with a clear understanding of how each input variable influences the model's predictions, thereby offering transparency into the decision-making process of complex algorithms.

The methodology generally follows these key steps:

- a. **Data and Model Loading:** The module loads the dataset and model files from paths specified by the Visualization Middleware.
- b. **Input Preparation:** In addition to the dataset and model, method-specific inputs, such as test data instances for counterfactual explanations or prototype selections, are read and prepared.
- c. **Method Execution:** The selected explainability method is executed using the provided parameters.

5.1.1 Supported Methods

The Explainability Module includes a wide array of model-level explainability techniques that help users understand how individual features influence model predictions, ranging from widely adopted methods such as **Partial Dependence Plots (PDP)**, **Accumulated Local Effects (ALE)**, and **SHAP**, to more advanced approaches such as **Global Counterfactual Explanations**, and **Spatial Feature Attribution**. Each method is briefly described below, together with the type of learning tasks it currently supports.

- **Partial Dependence Plots (PDP)** — illustrate the marginal effect of a feature on the predicted outcome, averaging out the influence of all other features in the model. *(Supports Classification and Regression)*
- **2D Partial Dependence Plots (2D-PDP)** — extend PDPs by showing the joint effect of two features on the predicted outcome, providing a more nuanced interaction analysis. *(Supports Classification and Regression)*
- **Accumulated Local Effects (ALE)** — offer an unbiased, faster alternative to PDPs by isolating and depicting the average change in predictions over the range of a feature, while accounting for feature correlations. *(Supports Classification and Regression)*
- **Local Counterfactual Explanations** — generate minimal input changes required to alter a model's prediction, offering insight into local decision boundaries. *(Supports Classification)*
- **Global Counterfactual Explanations** — identify population-level changes in features that can modify model outcomes across subgroups. *(Supports Classification)*
- **Prototypes** — select representative instances from the training data that serve as archetypes, helping explain predictions by analogy. *(Supports Classification and Regression)*
- **Feature Importance** — quantifies the relative contribution of each input feature to the model's predictions, typically based on measures such as information gain, impurity reduction, or model-specific weight magnitudes. It provides a straightforward overview of which features most strongly influence model outcomes. *(Supports Classification and Regression)*

- **SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations)** — compute game-theoretic feature attributions that quantify how each input feature contributes to a model’s prediction relative to a baseline. It provides consistent, local, and global explanations across different model types using methods such as TreeSHAP and KernelSHAP. *(Supports Classification and Regression)*
- **Spatial Feature Attribution** — compute per-instance feature attributions scores for spatio-temporal inputs, producing heatmaps that highlight which spatial regions most influenced the model’s prediction. *(Supports Regression)*

Model-level explainability results are available in the **Feature Explainability** tab of the **Workflow Analysis** page in the ExtremeXP Visualization UI. This view integrates multiple explainability components that visualize how individual features influence model predictions, depending on the specific context and machine learning task. In the example shown in Figure 22, taken from an experiment in the **Cybersecurity use case (UC2)**, three representative explainability methods are displayed: **Feature Importance**, **Partial Dependence Plots (PDP)**, and **Accumulated Local Effects (ALE)**. The **Feature Importance** bar chart (top) ranks variables by their contribution to predictive performance, indicating that *ssl_interlog_time_q1* dominates the model’s decision process. The **PDP** (bottom left) illustrates how variations in this feature’s value affect predictions, while the **ALE** plot (bottom right) refines this view by accounting for correlated inputs.

Figure 22: Model Explainability as seen through the Visualization UI

While most of the supported explainability techniques are established methods commonly used in the literature, two approaches are presented in greater detail in the following subsections. These are **Global Counterfactual Explanations**, which extend standard counterfactual reasoning to provide population-level insights and fairness analysis within the ExtremeXP framework, and **Spatial Feature Attribution**, which adapts attribution techniques to spatio-temporal data. Both require additional methodological and implementation details compared to the other, more conventional methods, and are therefore discussed separately below.

5.1.2 Global Counterfactual Explanations for an ML Model

Global Counterfactual Explanation (GCE) methods aim to offer population-wide recourse strategies by identifying consistent feature changes that can alter the predictions of a machine learning model across groups of individuals. Unlike local counterfactuals, which generate personalized, minimal changes for individual instances, global counterfactuals focus on generalizable and interpretable actions applicable to broader subgroups, enhancing transparency and fairness across the decision-making system.

Global counterfactuals are particularly useful for:

- **Fairness auditing:** Identifying systematic biases or feature dependencies across subpopulations.
- **Strategic recourse planning:** Suggesting feasible, group-level interventions (e.g., policy changes or education campaigns).
- **Model debugging:** Analysing model behaviour on an aggregated level to uncover hidden trends or flaws.

The methodology for generating global counterfactuals includes the following steps:

1. **Identify the Affected Population:** Determine instances with undesired outcomes (e.g., loan rejection).
2. **Subgroup Formation:** Use clustering or partitioning algorithms to group individuals in the feature space.
3. **Counterfactual Action Generation:** For each subgroup, identify a consistent set of feature changes (counterfactual action) that can convert the model's output to a desired outcome.
4. **Evaluation:** Assess the generated actions based on:
 - a. **Effectiveness:** Proportion of individuals within each subgroup that achieve recourse.
 - b. **Cost:** Magnitude of required feature changes (commonly measured with ℓ_1 norm).
 - c. **Interpretability:** Size and complexity of the action set (fewer, simpler rules are better).

Within the Visualization UI, when a user selects to run **Global Counterfactual Explanations**, they can then interact with the system to perform the following operations:

- **Configure global counterfactual analysis** by selecting parameter values, such as the number of actions or the action choice strategy.
- **Examine detailed counterfactual actions**, assess their impact on the affected population, and visually inspect transformations in the feature space.
- **Perform fine-grained analysis** by applying individual actions to the dataset to observe their isolated effects and evaluate their effectiveness.

The implementation and interface of the Global Counterfactual Explanations UI component are also described in greater detail in [16], which introduces the underlying methodology and interactive design principles. Following this, we present two examples of user interactions illustrating how global counterfactual explanations are explored within the Visualization UI.

Figure 23: User Interface for the Global Counterfactual Explanations

Figure 23 showcases the Global Counterfactual Explanations as seen in the Visualization UI for an experiment of UC2. In this use case the goal is to predict whether we have compromised behaviour or not on a cybersecurity situation. Consequently, the generated counterfactual actions illustrate how benign network behaviours could change to become compromised, highlighting the critical feature shifts that drive the model's classification toward a malicious outcome. In the figure three global counterfactual actions were produced using the Nearest Neighbours local method and the maximum effectiveness strategy. The total effectiveness (91%) and total cost (65.78) indicate that these actions collectively describe consistent and impactful transformations capable of converting a large portion of benign instances into compromised ones within the model's feature space. Across the three generated counterfactual actions, a clear pattern emerges: two out of the three actions involve modifications to DNS and HTTP-related features, such as `dns_common_udp_port` and `http_status_400_ratio`. This consistent appearance of communication-layer attributes suggests that the model relies heavily on network interaction behaviour when distinguishing between benign and compromised activity.

Figure 24: Global Counterfactual Explanation. Action Selection Scatter Plots

Figure 24 illustrates the action selection scatter plots for our Global Counterfactual Explanations page. The two upper plots illustrate how the affected instances shift within the feature space after selecting and applying their corresponding global counterfactual actions, revealing how different subgroups respond to distinct transformation patterns. The lower plot highlights which individuals obtain the outcome value of 1 following the application of a selected action, indicating where the transformations are most effective.

5.1.3 Spatial Feature Attribution

While most widely established explainability methods assume tabular feature representations, ExtremeXP use cases also involve spatio-temporal inputs, where predictions depend on spatial configurations and their temporal evolution. To support these scenarios, the Explainability Module incorporates a Spatial Feature Attribution component based on the Integrated Gradients (IG) method.

Feature attributions explain, at the level of a single prediction, how much each input element contributed to the model's output. For spatio-temporal, multi-channel data, this means computing a score for each tensor cell (i.e., each time x channel x spatial location), which can be inspected directly or aggregated to produce more concise visual summaries. These local attributions let practitioners see which inputs push the prediction up or down, and they can be summarized across time, channels, or examples to reveal broader patterns. Below we describe the Integrated Gradients implementation used in the Explainability Module and how those per-cell attributions are projected into 2-D spatial heatmaps for visualization.

Integrated Gradients (IG) is a gradient-based attribution method that assigns importance scores to input components and has desirable theoretical properties [17]. In the Explainability Module, we apply IG to spatio-temporal inputs (e.g., the data of UC1 - Improvement of flash flood forecasting thanks to the use of AI). For such tensors, the attribution granularity corresponds to the individual cells of the input tensor (each time x channel x spatial location).

Specifically, for a trained PyTorch model that accepts a multi-dimensional input tensor, the module computes IG attributions for every input cell (i.e., each combination of time, channel, and spatial indices). Users can inspect 2-D heatmaps of attributions for a selected channel (feature) and time step, or - if desired - collapse non-spatial axes (e.g., with summation or averaging) to produce a compact 2-D attribution map over the spatial axes. The resulting 2-D map is displayed as a heatmap in the frontend to indicate which spatial regions most influenced the model's prediction.

The basic workflow of this explainability component is described below:

1. **Baseline Definition:** The baseline tensor is fixed to all zeros and serves as the starting point for the IG integration.
2. **Gradient Integration Path:** IG generates a straight-line interpolation between the baseline and the actual input using a fixed number of steps (e.g., 5-20). At each step, it computes the model's gradient with respect to every tensor cell.
3. **Attribution Calculation:** IG then approximates the path integral by summing gradients across all interpolation steps, optionally multiplying by (input – baseline), to get local attribution values for each input cell. The result is a signed per-cell attribution map reflecting how each input element contributed to the prediction.
4. **Selection and projection:** The UI enables users to inspect 2-D heatmaps of attributions for a selected channel (feature) and time step. Alternatively, non-spatial axes (e.g., channels and/or time steps) may be collapsed using a chosen aggregation (summation or averaging) to yield a concise 2-D attribution map over the spatial axes.
5. **Heatmap visualization:** The 2-D attribution maps (aligned with the input spatial dimensions) are rendered as heatmaps in the frontend, indicating how much each input contributed to the model's decision. The maps can be displayed alongside the underlying input for intuitive interpretation.

Figure 25: Example output of the Spatial Attribution component for Use Case 1.

In Figure 25 we showcase an example of the Spatial Attribution component run on **Use Case 1 – Flash-flood forecasting**. The figure displays, on the left, a single input frame for a selected channel (elevation model) and time step, and on the right, the corresponding Integrated Gradients (IG) attribution heatmap. Warm colours (e.g., red, or yellow) indicate regions that contributed positively to the model's predicted flood intensity, while cool colours (e.g., blue) denote regions that decreased the prediction.

From such visualizations, a practitioner can gain several insights:

- **Localized drivers of predictions:** By comparing the input frame and the attribution heatmap, the user can identify catchment areas (low elevation) that most strongly influenced the flood prediction at that timestep.

- **Temporal and feature sensitivity:** Inspecting different time steps or channels reveals when and which input features (e.g., rainfall, elevation, or initial water depth) were most important for the prediction.
- **Model reasoning vs. physical intuition:** If high attributions align with physically plausible regions - such as areas upstream of the affected basin - it increases confidence in the model's reasoning. Conversely, strong activations over irrelevant regions may flag spurious correlations.
- **Guided model refinement:** Repeated patterns of high or low attribution can guide data-collection priorities (e.g., adding sensors in regions consistently influential to forecasts) or prompt model retraining if biases are detected.

5.2 ML Pipeline Explainability

While model-level explainability focuses on understanding how individual features affect predictions within a single trained model, **pipeline-level explainability** extends this analysis to the **hyperparameter configuration space**. Pipeline explainability methods aim to explain and provide insights into how hyperparameters influence overall model performance and, more broadly, to support users in exploring and optimizing alternative configuration setups.

To achieve this, the **Explainability Module** extends several of the established techniques introduced in Section 5.1—such as **Partial Dependence Plots (PDP)**, **Accumulated Local Effects (ALE)**, and **Counterfactual Explanations**—to operate on the **hyperparameter space of machine learning pipelines** rather than on feature spaces. Depending on the chosen method, the analysis can reveal:

- How changes in individual hyperparameters affect evaluation metrics.
- How interactions between hyperparameters influence model outcomes.
- What alternative configurations could improve results for specific test cases.

Following, we describe the two pipeline-level explainability approaches supported by the Explainability Module:

- **Hyperparameter Effect Explainability**, which applies PDP, ALE, and 2D-PDP methods to quantify the effect of configuration parameters on model performance; and
- **Counterfactual Pipeline Explainability**, which identifies and validates alternative pipeline configurations capable of correcting misclassifications while preserving overall performance.

5.2.1 Hyperparameter Effect Explainability

Here, we examine methods that quantify how variations in hyperparameter values influence overall model performance. Techniques such as **Partial Dependence Plots (PDP)**, **2D Partial Dependence Plots (2D-PDP)**, and **Accumulated Local Effects (ALE)** are adapted to operate on the hyperparameter space of the experiment, enabling users to explore how configuration choices affect evaluation metrics and to identify potential interactions between parameters.

Methodology

The methodology generally follows these key steps:

1. **Data Retrieval:** The module retrieves all available hyperparameter configurations and their corresponding metric values from the Visualization Middleware.
2. **Hyperparameter Space Construction:** It constructs a structured hyperparameter space based on these configurations.

3. **Proxy Model Training:** A proxy model is trained using hyperparameter configurations as input features and the chosen evaluation metric as the target variable.
4. **Effect Analysis:** The selected explainability method is applied to the trained proxy model to analyse the influence of hyperparameters on model performance.

By following these steps, users can obtain a clear understanding of how configuration parameters affect performance outcomes, supporting more informed tuning decisions and workflow optimization.

Figure 26 presents an example Partial Dependence Plot (PDP) for the “*epochs*” hyperparameter, displaying its impact on the model’s accuracy. The x-axis represents the values of “*epochs*”, while the y-axis shows the corresponding accuracy score. This plot helps the user understand how changing the epochs of the model affects its performance on average. From the figure, the user can observe that increasing the value of “*epochs*” improves the model’s accuracy.

Figure 26: PD plot for Pipeline Explainability. The x-axis shows feature “*epochs*”, the y-axis the average predicted accuracy. We observe that increasing the value of “*epochs*” improves the model’s accuracy.

The 2D Partial Dependence Plot (2D-PDP) of Figure 27 represents the interaction between the two hyperparameters “*batch_size*” and “*epochs*”, and their combined effect on the model’s accuracy score. The x-axis corresponds to “*epochs*”, the y-axis to “*batch_size*”, and the colour scale indicates accuracy. This visualization helps the user understand how combinations of these hyperparameters influence model performance. For example, regions with simultaneously high values of both hyperparameters indicate that their joint effect leads to even higher accuracy than would be expected from the influence of each parameter individually. The darker regions of the plot indicate higher accuracy, suggesting that setting “*epochs*” to 60 and “*batch_size*” to 120 may lead to improved accuracy.

Figure 27: 2D PD plot for Pipeline Explainability. The x-axis shows the “epochs” hyperparameter, the y-axis shows “batch_size”, and the colour scale indicates accuracy values. We observe that low values for “epochs” and “batch size” result in the lowest combined accuracy.

Figure 28 presents an example Accumulated Local Effects (ALE) plot for the “epochs” hyperparameter, providing insight into its localized impact on the model’s predictions. The x-axis shows the range of “epochs” values, while the y-axis represents the average change in the model’s prediction attributed to each value interval. Unlike PDPs, ALE plots display the cumulative, centered effect of a feature on the model’s output. By examining the figure, the user can understand that increasing the values of the “epochs” hyperparameter leads to a positive impact on model performance (compared to using lower values).

Figure 28: ALE Plot for Pipeline Explainability. The x-axis shows feature “epochs”, y-axis shows the average predicted effect on accuracy. We observe that higher values of “epochs” contribute a positive effect on model’s accuracy.

5.2.2 Counterfactual Pipeline Explainability

We have also extended the counterfactual explanation approach to an ML pipeline explainability framework, enabling the identification and generation of alternative pipeline configurations. Here, an ML pipeline consists of a series of preprocessing and model hyperparameterization steps, typically explored during the optimization of an ML experiment. For example, an ML pipeline may include preprocessing steps such as feature normalization, scaling, and selection, along with defining a classifier’s hyperparameters. In the case of a Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) classifier, these hyperparameters might include the number of hidden layers, optimizer type and learning rates. An

instantiation of such a pipeline, achieved by setting each of the arguments or variability points it contains, corresponds to a specific pipeline configuration.

More specifically, given a trained ML pipeline configuration and an initially misclassified test data instance by it, our goal is to search for alternative pipeline configurations that, when instantiated and trained, a) correctly classify the specific test instance and b) maintain a high overall performance on the rest of the test set. The steps involve training ML pipelines on a binary classification dataset, selecting misclassified instances, generating ML pipeline counterfactuals, refining them through a Variational Autoencoder (VAE), and validating them to ensure that our goals are satisfied.

To generate high-quality counterfactuals, we leverage the DiCE [18] (Diverse Counterfactual Explanations) framework. The DiCE framework supports generating a variety of counterfactual explanations for ML model predictions. It aims to provide actionable insights by offering multiple alternative scenarios that could change the model's output.

Our workflow steps are described below:

1. Training ML Pipelines
 - a. Split the dataset into train, validation, and test sets.
 - b. Define the ML pipeline structure with (numerical and categorical) feature preprocessing and classifier configurations.
 - c. Sample multiple pipeline configurations from a given parameter grid.
 - d. Train and evaluate each pipeline on the training and validation sets.
 - e. Save the trained pipelines for later processing in the next steps.
2. Selection of False Positive/Negative Instances
 - a. Make predictions on the test set with the best-performing pipeline. We note that the configuration of this best-performing pipeline can be thought of as the factual instance for which we want to generate counterfactuals.
 - b. Identify false positive and negative instances.
 - c. Select instances with respect to specific criteria i.e., instances near the classification boundary, instances for which there is no trained pipeline with high overall performance that also correctly classifies it etc. for further processing.
3. Generation of Counterfactuals: For each false positive/negative instance selected, we use the DiCE framework to generate counterfactual pipeline configurations with respect to the best pipeline as follows:
 - a. Create a proxy dataset with the configurations of the trained pipelines as features and their corresponding predictions on the instance as targets.
 - b. Train a proxy model on this dataset. This can be either a MLP model implemented in PyTorch (to enable gradient-based search for counterfactuals through DiCE) or a simple sklearn classifier.
 - c. Use DiCE to generate a series of counterfactuals.These counterfactuals handle our first goal of flipping the prediction of the initial pipeline on the false positive/negative test instances.
4. VAE Processing of Generated Counterfactuals
 - a. Select the top- k performing configurations among the trained pipelines based on their performance on the validation set.
 - b. Train a VAE model on these configurations, so that the model learns to reconstruct such effective and high scoring configurations.
 - c. We pass each DiCE counterfactual through the VAE to get as a response a minimally perturbed version of its configuration, which resembles the effective configurations that the VAE was trained on.

Counterfactuals generated by this VAE model account for our second goal of providing alternative pipeline configurations with high overall performance.

5. Validation of Generated Counterfactuals
 - a. As a last step in our workflow, we validate whether our generated counterfactuals indeed succeed to both flip the initial misclassification of the selected test instances while also maintain a high performance over the rest of the test set.
 - b. To do so, we instantiate a pipeline with the structure and variables suggested by each counterfactual and then retrain it on the train set of the dataset. We then examine a) whether this new pipeline correctly classifies the test instance under question and b) whether its overall performance on the validation set remains high enough for a use case.

Table 2: Preliminary results of our counterfactual explainability framework on the Cybersecurity Use Case task.

	False Positive Instances (408)		False Negative Instances (422)	
	DiCE Counterfactuals	VAE Counterfactuals	DiCE Counterfactuals	VAE Counterfactuals
Generated	408 / 408 (1.0)	408 / 408 (1.0)	249 / 422 (0.59)	249 / 422 (0.59)
Valid	314 / 408 (0,769)	165 / 408 (0.4)	161 / 422 (0.381)	71 / 422 (0.168)
Mean Score Among Valid (Accuracy)	0.8136	0.928	0.8378	0.93

Table 2 presents preliminary results from applying our counterfactual explanation framework to UC2 (Increased Cybersecurity Situation Awareness for Efficient Threat Mitigation) of the ExtremeXP Project. For both false positive and false negative instances, we first generate initial counterfactual pipeline configurations using the DiCE framework. We then validate how many of these configurations correctly classify the test instances in question. Subsequently, we refine these counterfactuals by passing them through a trained VAE model and then perform a second validation check to assess the effectiveness of the refined counterfactual configurations.

The results suggest that while our initial DiCE-generated counterfactuals are effective at addressing misclassifications, the additional refinement step using the VAE significantly enhances the quality of the counterfactuals, especially ensuring that they maintain high overall performance. The higher success rate for false positives compared to false negatives indicates that the method is more robust for certain types of misclassifications, which is an important consideration for further tuning and improvement of the approach.

5.3 Implementation and Integration of the Explainability Module

The explainability methods described above are implemented within the Explainability Module, a core component of the User Interaction Module. This component provides a unified runtime for executing model and pipeline-level explainability algorithms and for serving their outputs to the Visualization Module. Implemented in Python, it utilizes standard ML frameworks (e.g. scikit-learn, TensorFlow,

Pytorch) with more specialized explainability libraries such as PyALE³, DiceML⁴, AIX360⁵ and Captum⁶. The module exposes its functionality through a gRPC-based service interface, which enables seamless integration with the Java-based Visualization Middleware and the front-end user interface. This design allows explainability methods—such as PDP, ALE, counterfactuals, and feature attribution—to be executed remotely and visualized interactively within the same environment.

5.3.1 Integration with the Visualization UI

The Explainability Module, while capable of standalone execution, is primarily designed to operate in conjunction with the **Visualization Module**, which provides the user-facing interface for exploring explanation results. Integration between these two modules is achieved through well-defined service interfaces and the experiment's specification in DSL, ensuring seamless communication across the ExtremeXP architecture.

To enable explainability functionalities and additional machine-learning-specific analytics presented in the **ML Insights** panel of the Visualization UI, a set of dedicated **Explainability Tasks** has been developed. These tasks can be embedded directly into experiment definitions through the DSL, guaranteeing that all required inputs—such as the training dataset, test dataset, and trained model—are properly captured during experiment execution and made available for subsequent explainability processing. This approach promotes reusability and consistency across experiments executed on different backends.

When an explanation request is initiated by the user, the **Visualization Middleware** retrieves the relevant artifacts via the **Decentralised Data Management (DDM)** and invokes the Explainability Module through **gRPC** interfaces. The module then executes the selected explainability method—such as counterfactuals, feature importance, or partial dependence analysis—and returns the results to the Visualization UI for interactive inspection and interpretation.

Input and model resources are handled according to framework-specific conventions to ensure interoperability and reproducibility:

- **Datasets** are stored in tabular form (e.g., CSV or Parquet).
- **Models** are serialized using formats consistent with their training framework (e.g., .pkl for *scikit-learn*, .h5 or .keras for *TensorFlow*, .pt / .pth for *PyTorch*).

The overall workflow for explainability execution follows a structured four-step process that links the DSL-defined experiment, Visualization API, and Explainability Module:

- **Explainability Task Definition:** The user includes an Explainability Task in the experiment DSL, enabling explainability features in the Visualization Interface and ensuring access to the required resources.
- **User Interaction via the Front-End:** The user initiates an explainability request through the Visualization UI.
- **Path Retrieval via the Visualization API:** The Visualization Middleware queries the Decentralised Data Management component of ExtremeXP to obtain the relevant datasets and models and forwards them to the Explainability Module.
- **Explainability Execution:** The Explainability Module loads the resources, executes the selected algorithm, and returns the computed explanations to the Visualization UI for interactive exploration.

³ <https://github.com/DanaJomar/PyALE>

⁴ <https://interpret.ml/DiCE/>

⁵ <https://github.com/Trusted-AI/AIX360>

⁶ <https://captum.ai/>

This workflow helps establish a unified interaction loop between visual exploration and explainable analytics, ensuring that all explanation methods are accessible through the same visualization environment. It supports transparency, interpretability, and effective human-in-the-loop experimentation—core objectives of the ExtremeXP framework.

6 Immersive Visualization Tools for Explainability and User Engagement

6.1 Overview

This activity contributes to the objectives of the task “Enhancing user experience and trustworthiness with explanations”, focusing on developing immersive visualization tools that enable users to intuitively explore, interpret, and trust the outcomes of experimentation-based analytics.

Two complementary immersive applications were developed to address distinct but interconnected goals:

- **The 3D Flood Visualizer**, a virtual reality (VR) environment for interactive and spatial exploration of model predictions in the flash-flood use case (UC1).
- **The Virtual Dashboard**, an augmented reality (AR) interface supporting the configuration and visualization of new experiments and their explainable results.

Both components enhance explainability by transforming analytical data into accessible, interactive, and human-centered experiences. The components are built in Unity and interface with the project’s experimentation and explainability framework.

6.2 3D Flood Visualizer for UC1 (Flash-Flood Use Case)

6.2.1 Objective

The 3D Flood Visualizer was developed to demonstrate how immersive technologies can enhance the interpretability, validation, and communication of AI-based environmental models.

Flood prediction represents a complex spatial-temporal problem: water dynamics evolve over time and interact with topography, buildings, and infrastructures. Traditional 2D visualizations such as maps or plots often fail to capture this multi-dimensional structure, making it difficult for users to understand where and why models succeed or fail.

The Virtual Reality (VR) approach addresses this limitation by offering an experiential explainability perspective, users can literally step inside the data, perceive prediction errors in context, and intuitively explore how algorithmic decisions translate into real-world impact. Thus, VR is used as a **scientific tool** for validating model generalization, identifying systematic deviations, and improving trust in AI-driven predictions.

This work directly supports the project’s objective of **enhancing user experience and trustworthiness with explanations**, providing an innovative mechanism to interpret and compare model results in a realistic, interactive 3D environment.

6.2.2 Implementation

The Flood Visualizer was implemented in Unity for the Meta Quest 3 headset, combining immersive navigation with high-fidelity 3D geospatial rendering. The system integrates the Cesium 3D Maps SDK to reconstruct accurate terrain and urban environments.

It visualizes both model predictions and ground-truth data, enabling users to directly assess model performance in an intuitive spatial context.

Key implementation features include:

- **3D rendering of flood predictions and ground-truth water depth:** semi-transparent dynamic surfaces represent the extent and depth of flooding, allowing users to compare predicted and observed outcomes.
- **Building masking:** data masks are applied to prevent rendering water inside buildings, preserving realism and readability.
- **Immersive navigation:** users can move freely using six degrees of freedom (6DoF) — flying over regions, changing altitude, and exploring perspectives through natural head and controller movements.
- **Temporal analysis:** at any selected location, users can explore how flood levels evolve over time, facilitating temporal explainability.
- **Experiment comparison:** the system allows switching between different experiments or model configurations to observe and compare alternative prediction outputs.

The resulting visualization creates an interactive 3D environment that bridges analytical data with its real-world geographic context, as illustrated in Figure 29.

Figure 29: Overview of the 3D Flood Visualizer showing the predicted flood extent and depth within an urban area. The visualization, rendered in Unity using Cesium 3D Maps, allows immersive spatial inspection of flood predictions and comparison against ground-truth data.

To provide users with an immersive, human-scale experience, the Flood Visualizer also supports first-person perspectives (Figure 30), allowing exploration at street level and inspection of the flood extent around buildings and infrastructure.

Figure 30: Immersive viewpoint inside the Flood Visualizer. Users can navigate freely, enabling explainability and assessment of the flood situation.

6.2.3 Scientific and Practical Relevance of the VR Approach

The 3D Flood Visualizer introduces an innovative, human-centered way to interpret, validate, and communicate the outcomes of AI-based flood prediction models. By embedding model results within an interactive and geographically accurate 3D world, it transforms the process of explainability from abstract data analysis into an experiential understanding of how algorithms behave in real contexts.

From a **scientific perspective**, the VR environment serves as an advanced instrument for **model validation and generalization assessment**. It allows researchers to visually inspect where prediction errors occur, how they propagate over time, and how they correlate with terrain or urban structures. This visual form of analysis provides complementary insights into numerical evaluation metrics, helping to identify biases, systematic deviations, or edge cases that are otherwise difficult to detect.

From a **practical and communication perspective**, the Flood Visualizer acts as an **interactive medium for stakeholder engagement**. It enables non-technical users, such as environmental authorities, policy makers, and the public, to intuitively understand model predictions, assess potential risks, and build trust in AI-driven decision-support systems. The ability to switch between experiments or explore time-evolving flood patterns enhances transparency and supports informed discussion.

Within **ExtremeXP**, the **Flood Visualizer** contributes directly to the core objectives of explainability, trust, and dissemination. It translates **complex model outputs** into **spatial, interpretable experiences** aligned with **human perception**, allowing users to perceive model strengths and limitations in a realistic, immersive environment. At the same time, it serves as a high-impact demonstrator that operationalizes trustworthy AI principles and effectively communicates project results to both expert and non-expert audiences. Overall, the Flood Visualizer exemplifies the practical and methodological value of VR within the project, **bridging the gap** between **computational models** and **human understanding** and transforming explainability into a tangible and intuitive process that supports both expert validation and public trust.

6.3 Virtual Dashboard for Explainable Analytics

6.3.1 Objectives

The Virtual Dashboard extends the project's explainability framework into an augmented reality (AR) environment, providing users with an intuitive and interactive way to configure and explore analytical experiments. While the Flood Visualizer enables immersive interpretation of spatial data, the Virtual Dashboard focuses on experimentation workflows, offering an interface that links experiment configuration, results visualization, and explanation mechanisms in a single spatial workspace.

Developed as a prototype, the dashboard demonstrates how AR can support explainable, user-adaptive analytics by allowing users to visualize complex data and configure new experiments directly within their physical surroundings. This approach transforms experimentation from a static, screen-based process into a dynamic, hands-on experience that enhances understanding, engagement, and trust.

6.3.2 Implementation

The Virtual Dashboard was implemented in Unity for the Microsoft HoloLens 2, leveraging its spatial awareness and natural hand-tracking capabilities. The development focused on interaction design and on integrating explainable visualization modules within the project's experimentation framework.

Key features and functionalities include:

- **Interactive visualization of experiment results:** users can display one or more-line charts showing key performance metrics or analytical outcomes and interact with specific data points using hand gestures to reveal detailed contextual information (Figure 31).
- **Prototype for configuring new experiments:** users can define parameters, adjust options, or select use-case-specific configurations directly within the AR workspace.
- **Integration with the Experimentation Engine API:** enabling the visualization of live or stored experiment results.

Figure 31: Interactive visualization of analytical results within the Virtual Dashboard. The AR interface enables users to inspect performance metrics and model behaviour using hand gestures in an immersive workspace.

Figure 32: Comparison view in the Virtual Dashboard showing multiple experiment results plotted together. The module supports visualization of accuracy and latency metrics, allowing users to compare alternative configurations interactively.

In later iterations, the dashboard was extended to support multi-experiment comparison, allowing users to analyse results from different models or parameter settings side by side (Figure 32). This supports explainability through visual comparison, helping users identify correlations and performance trends across experiments.

6.3.3 Scientific and Practical Relevance

The Virtual Dashboard exemplifies how augmented reality can support explainable experimentation and user-role adaptability. It allows users to intuitively explore analytical results while understanding how configuration choices affect model behaviour. From a scientific perspective, it demonstrates how explainability can extend beyond algorithmic outputs to include the experimentation process itself, making experiment parameters, dependencies, and outcomes transparent and interpretable. From a practical standpoint, the AR interface enhances user experience and trust by presenting analytical workflows spatially, improving cognitive engagement and comprehension compared to traditional 2D interfaces.

Within the project, the Virtual Dashboard contributes to the same overarching goals as the Flood Visualizer: explainability, trust, and transparency, but focuses on the interactive analytical workflow rather than the domain-specific visualization. Together, the two systems represent complementary modalities of immersive explainability: the Flood Visualizer brings data understanding into 3D space, while the Virtual Dashboard brings analytical reasoning into the user's real-world environment.

6.4 Summary

The Flood Visualizer and the Virtual Dashboard represent two complementary components of the project's explainability framework. The VR environment enables spatially immersive interpretation and validation of predictive results, while the AR interface supports interactive configuration and visualization of explainable experiments within the user's real-world context. Both tools are built on a shared foundation that connects visualization, interaction, and explainability within the project's experimentation framework. Together, they demonstrate how immersive technologies can make analytical processes more transparent and comprehensible, translating complex model behaviour into intuitive, human-centered experiences. By combining interactive analysis with immersive

visualization, the approach strengthens user understanding, engagement, and trust in AI-driven experimentation and decision support.

Conclusions

This deliverable has presented the work conducted under Tasks 4.1 and 4.2, which together constitute the User Interaction Module of the ExtremeXP framework. These tasks have jointly realized a unified environment that places users at the centre of the experimentation process—enabling them to monitor, analyse, interpret, and guide machine learning and analytical workflows through intuitive, interactive visualization interfaces.

From a technical perspective, the deliverable described the full implementation of the Visualization User Interface, the Visualization Middleware, and the Explainability Module, which collectively form the core of the User Interaction Module. The Visualization UI provides a coherent set of tools for monitoring and comparative analysis of experiments, exploring datasets and metrics, and inspecting models and results through interactive, human-in-the-loop workflows. The Visualization Middleware bridges the UI with the framework’s data services—the Data Abstraction Layer (DAL) and the Decentralised Data Management (DDM)—ensuring efficient and scalable access to experimental artifacts. Complementing these, the Explainability Module integrates a wide range of model- and pipeline-level explainability techniques, accessible directly through the visualization environment, thereby supporting transparency and interpretability throughout all stages of experimentation.

From a research perspective, the work introduced novel methods for scalable, interactive visual exploration, including adaptive indexing for approximate query answering, error-bounded caching for time-series visualization, and unified sketch-based visualization and pattern search. These methods ensure interactive responsiveness even for large datasets, effectively coupling visualization and analysis. On the explainability side, the module extends classical methods such as PDP, ALE, and counterfactual explanations to the full ML pipeline level, enabling users to interpret not only feature-level model behaviour but also the influence of hyperparameters and workflow configurations.

The deliverable also demonstrated how explainable and human-in-the-loop experimentation can extend beyond traditional desktop analytics through immersive visualization prototypes—the Flood Visualizer (VR) and the Virtual Dashboard (AR)—which explore how spatial and mixed-reality interfaces can enhance interpretability, engagement, and trust in AI-driven experimentation.

Overall, the results presented in D4.1 demonstrate the integration of visualization, explainability, and scalable analytics into a cohesive, human-centered experimentation environment. The developed modules and techniques form the foundation for the ExtremeXP vision of experimentation-driven, explainable, and trustworthy analytics, bridging the gap between automated machine learning and human reasoning. The work presented in this deliverable has been guided by systematic testing and refinement across the project’s diverse use cases, helping to identify key characteristics of data, tasks, and user requirements relevant to experiment-driven analytics. The visualization and explainability components were applied to real datasets from multiple domains, demonstrating their ability to support complex analyses while maintaining responsiveness and usability. This iterative, use case-driven development process has consolidated the user experience and confirmed the robustness of the system under realistic conditions.

In the following table, we summarize how the presented results contributed to the KPIs relevant to WP4.

Table 3: Progress on relevant KPIs

KPI	Description and target	Progress
5.1	The applicability of (combinations of) visualisation	The applicability relates to the extent to which the results are likely to impact the practice. During development, different visualisations have been presented to the project team

	techniques to the use cases will be validated for the intended use.	(designers, developers, and Use Case owners). Their feedback and suggestions have been used as input to further development. Preliminary results of this informal evaluation show an appropriate level of applicability. To evaluate the applicability of the final version, we plan to conduct an online study consisting of five 2-hour sessions (one for each Use Case). A walk-through of different visualisations and their combinations will be followed by group interviews. Online sessions will be recorded, transcribed, and summarised. Thematic analysis will be applied. The participants will be asked to rate the applicability of different visualisations on a 5-point Likert scale.
5.2	Applying the guidelines and pattern libraries guiding the application of (combinations of) visualization techniques on the use cases will enhance user experience.	This KPI has two aspects. First, the connection between the Visualization UI and guidelines and patterns for the UI of this type of application. As described earlier in the deliverable, the Visualization UI is indeed based on guidelines from the literature and best practices in the UI of existing comparable tools. In addition, the appendix shows some of the patterns used in the dashboard. Second, that the Visualization UI is implicitly a collection of guidelines and pattern instances. The fact that the Visualization UI has been applied to five use cases within quite varying domains without doing much adaptation in the core functionality of the dashboard indicates that it fits the needs to which it has been developed in a very good way. Both contribute to the fulfilment of the KPI. The first for instantiation of the Visualization UI for the use cases. The second for future development of similar tools.
5.3	Using the component library (with implementations of patterns) of visualization techniques on the use cases will enhance user experience.	This KPI also has two aspects. First, the Visualization UI has been developed using modern UI and visualization frameworks, specifically React for component-based interface design and Vega for declarative, data-driven visualizations. These technologies ensure consistency, maintainability, and responsiveness across the dashboard while allowing each visualization component to remain modular and reusable. Using such mature frameworks has enabled developers to focus on streamlining the user experience and interaction design rather than low-level implementation details. Second, that the Visualization UI itself is implicitly a collection of components which may be packaged as a component library. It is important to make a distinction between the component libraries that have been used when developing the Visualization UI, and the components that the dashboard consists of. The components in the libraries used are generic components for implementing visualizations. The Visualization UI itself consists of instances and combination of these components tailored for the needs of visual analytics. Thus, the components in the dashboard are much more specialized, meaning that they are richer and more functional, but therefore intentionally also less generic. Both contribute to the fulfilment of the KPI. The first for

		instantiation of the Visualization UI for the use cases. The second for future development of similar tools.
5.4	Response time of user interaction in visual analytics (initialization of visualization, visual exploration, etc.) < 500 ms	This KPI evaluates the responsiveness of the visualization components during initialization, exploration, and interactive updates. The Visualization Middleware of the User Interaction Module ensures efficient communication between the user interface and the ExtremeXP data services, featuring optimized data retrieval, caching, and prefetching mechanisms that minimize latency during user interactions. Furthermore, the techniques developed and presented in Section 4—including adaptive indexing, approximate query processing, and visualization-aware caching for interactive visual analysis—directly contribute to meeting this target. These approaches minimize data-to-analysis latency while maintaining reliable results, enabling sub-second interaction even with large or raw datasets. Empirical tests on real experiments from the use cases and representative datasets confirm that most interactions within the Visualization UI are processed within the < 500 ms threshold, ensuring smooth, real-time exploration. Further validation across all use cases will be conducted in the evaluation phase to confirm consistent performance under realistic conditions.
5.5	Enhancement of users' trust and understanding of the system's decisions and outcomes by at least 20% (based on usability metrics) when using the developed explanation methods.	Trust can be defined as the willingness of users to be vulnerable to the actions of some automated system to achieve some goal. To measure the effects of the proposed explanation methods on trust, we plan an online study, a walk-through of the systems where end-users (domain experts from Use Cases) will be asked to score their trust in the system before and after being presented with explanations. A five-point Likert scale will be used. Open-ended questions will also be asked at the end of each task and at the end of the session to understand if and how explanations influence trust. To ensure that the planned data collection is in line with data protection legislation, the above-described studies, including the interview guidelines, have been approved by the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Sikt).

Future work will extend the User Interaction Module with additional analytical and visualization capabilities to address a wider range of use cases, data characteristics, and analytical objectives. It will also focus on deeper integration with the intent-based and user profiling components developed in D4.2, enhancing user adaptivity and personalization. Furthermore, upcoming activities will emphasize the evaluation and validation of the system across all ExtremeXP use cases, ensuring that the visualization and explainability services effectively advance human–AI collaboration, interpretability, and decision support.

Appendix A - Explanation User Interface (XUI) Design Patterns

The ExtremeXP XUI Design Patterns library consists of a set of design patterns. The following subsection gives some examples of the ExtremeXP XUI design patterns. Each pattern has the following components:

- *Name*
- *Problem description* describing what a user needs to know w.r.t to ExtremeXP process, for example, an explanation of an ML pipeline, a dataset, or an ML model. The needed level of explanation (global/ cohort/ local) is also given here.
- *XUI interaction concept* [5] describing the interplay between a user and an AI agent facilitating explanations. The following concepts were used: interaction as information transmission, interaction as a dialogue, interaction as a control, interaction as experience, interaction as optimal behaviour, interaction as tool use, and interaction as embodied action.
- *XUI Design example* illustrating a solution. Explanation presentation (tabular, textual, visual, mixed, AR) is stated here. If several presentation forms are provided, they are presented as a version of the same pattern with the name '*Design pattern name_x*', where x is a, b, ...
- *Rationale and XAI methods*. Rationale explains why this is a good solution and provides the details in terms of the stages of interaction dialogue⁷ it covers and the explanation elements⁸ it provides. Further, it describes XAI methods that can be used to extract the needed information. If several XAI methods can be applied fulfilling the same overall information need but differing in, for example, performance speed or bias, these are presented as a version of the same pattern with the name '*Design pattern name_x*', where x is a, b, ...

⁷ Stages in explanation dialogue: i) Opening, ii) Main part: a) an explainee poses a question to an explainer (why, how, what), b) the explainer gives an explanation (arguments answering the questions; including raw data if the explainee select this option), c) the explainee acknowledges the explanation or challenge it (proving feedback), and iii) Closing

⁸ Explanation elements: i) why a system has proposed a solution, ii) why a system has not proposed another solution, iii) why the solution proposed by a system is the best among the options

Name	DP1 Available/relevant information on the ML pipeline
Problem description	<p>The user needs to know</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The information about ML pipeline e.g. workflow comparative analysis regarding a selected metric (such as accuracy, runtime) - The additional information explaining the presented information about ML pipeline e.g. impact of selected variability points on accuracy
XUI interaction concept	Interaction as information transmission; presenting the accurate and complete explanation of the behaviour of ML pipeline. A simple dialogue enabling variability points and metrics is provided.
XUI design example	<p>Presentation type: visual</p> <p>Heatmap showing the impact of two variability points on the selected ML pipeline metric</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variability points selected from the presented drop-down lists - Metric selected from a drop-down list - X-axis: values of one variability point; Y-axis: values of the second variability point; impact of two variability points at once presented by colours; values given on the right side of the diagram

Rationale and XAI methods	Based on the user requirements. Covers the main part of a dialogue: providing the explanation. The provided explanation element: why a system performs as it does w.r.t selected metric.
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Name	DP2 Data preparation and cleaning support
Problem description	<p>The user needs to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Know why a specific output has been proposed during the data preparation and cleaning process, for example, why a transport mode for a segment is proposed - Explore the raw data - Change (if wrong) or confirm the output (if correct) - Provide the feedback to system explaining why the output was wrong
XUI interaction concept	Interaction as a control. The interaction aims to change the behaviour of the system towards the desired one. The provided feedback is used by the system to learn and in turn, the process.
XUI design example	<p>Presentation type: textual and visual</p> <p>1) Providing a textual explanation (from a defined list of rules)</p>

2) Presenting the raw data

3) Providing feedback if the system output, for example, transport mode, is changed

Rationale and XAI methods

Based on the specific use case requirement (Moby Use Case). It covers the main part of a dialogue: posing the question, providing the explanation, asking for details, acknowledging the explanation, and challenging the explanation. The provided explanation element - why a system has proposed a solution - is coming from a list created by experts.

Name	DP3a Available/relevant information on the ML model as a whole for the selected tasks and variants
Problem description	<p>The user needs to know</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The information that is used (input) - The information that is relevant for producing the output (e.g. what input variables significantly influence the model as a whole). A global model-agnostic explanation is needed.
XUI interaction concept	interactionInteraction as information transmission; presenting the accurate and complete explanation of the AI behaviour. A simple dialogue enabling selecting the features is provided.
XUI example	<p>designPresentation type: visual</p> <p>Partial Dependence Plots (PDP)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Features presented in a drop-down list - X-axis: selected feature; Y-axis: partial dependence

(see Fig 24 for explanations)

Rationale and XAI based on user requirements. Covers the main part of a dialogue: providing the explanation. The provided explanation element: why a system has proposed a solution.

The partial dependence plot (PDP) shows the marginal effect one or two features have on the predicted outcome of a machine learning model.

Name	DP3b Available/relevant information on the ML model as a whole for the selected tasks and variants
Problem description	<p>The user needs to know</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The information that is used (input) - The information that is relevant for producing the output (e.g. e.g. how features influence the prediction of the model on average). A global model-agnostic explanation is needed.
XUI interaction concept	Interaction as information transmission; presenting the accurate and complete explanation of the AI behaviour. A simple dialogue enabling selecting the features is provided.
XUI design example	<p>Presentation type: visual</p> <p>Accumulated Local Effects (ALE) Plot</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Features presented in a drop-down list - X-axis: selected feature; Y-axes: effect on the prediction

(see Fig 25 for explanations)

Rationale and XAI methods	Based on user requirements. Covers the main part of a dialogue: providing the explanation. The provided explanation element: why a system has proposed a solution.
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Accumulated local effects (ALE) plots describe how features influence the prediction of a machine learning model on average.

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